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List of Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago, Ecuador (Version 2.0)

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Introduction

In preparation for the revised new edition of the 1997 book “The Fishes of the Galapagos Islands” by Jack Stein Grove and Robert J. Lavenberg, to be published next year by the EPCA, the East Pacific Corridor Alliance Foundation (www.epcafoundation.org), we have been reviewing literature and museum records and obtaining additional underwater photographs and specimens. A recent expedition sponsored by the EPCA in May 2024 conducted widespread surveys, and, in particular, intensive underwater photography and collecting for tissues for DNA sequencing (targeting cryptobenthic species, new records or species, and unresolved taxa). The fish species list published by us in Grove et al. (2022) is thus here updated, with a number of changes, mostly species added (usually deeper or mesopelagic species), but some species subtracted when we conclude evidence is lacking for inclusion, applying strict scientific criteria (see below). The total number of species listed is up to 683 from 644, the number of families is increased by 18 families to 178 (mostly added mesopelagic or deepwater families, a few taxonomic adjustments, and three removed).

Our updated list of fishes known to occur on and around the Archipelago are listed in Table 1 (in taxonomic order) and Table 2 (in family alphabetical order). We define the area as that encompassed by the Ecuadorean EEZ limits around the Galapagos Archipelago (Fig. 1), which extend well beyond the boundaries of the Galapagos Marine Reserve (Reserva Marina de Galápagos) and also include the new Reserva Marina Hermandad in the waters between Galapagos and the border of the Costa Rican EEZ limits around Cocos Island. The area covered includes the islands and adjoining shelf slope down to and including the abyssal region and the seamounts.

The present list includes 683 species of fishes, with 60 in Chondrichthyes (in 28 families) and 614 bony fishes (in 151 families), plus 8 hagfishes (Myxiniformes) and one cephalochordate (note Grove et al. (2022)

Figure 1. The bathymetric map of the Galapagos Archipelago and environs in the tropical eastern Pacific Ocean, showing the Ecuadorean Galapagos EEZ boundary ring. The orange diamond is the location of the larval collection from Victor (in press).

reported 56 chondrichthyans, but 61 (and 8 hagfishes) were in their list). Of the total, 77 are considered vagrants (3 chondrichthyans), many of which are Indo-Pacific coral-reef species that are sporadic, or even single, records. There are 67 documented endemic species (7 chondrichthyan species; 30 families of which 4 are chondrichthyans), about half deeper-water, benthic-associated species and the remainder mostly reef species with relatively short larval lives, such as blennioids, dactyloscopids, gobioids, and haemulids. For broad habitat categories, there are 260 shallow resident shorefishes (in 79 families) and 65 shallow shorefish vagrants (in 34 families, of which 7 are only vagrant: plus 12 non-shallow-shorefish vagrants); then 28 resident nearshore pelagics (Carangidae and Coryphaenidae); 121 deepwater non-pelagics (46 families); 96 offshore pelagics (38 families); and 112 mesopelagic species (30 families).

Methods

We evaluate whether each species comprises a resident population or can be considered a vagrant, defined as a species present as isolated individual(s) and likely not to be a self-recruiting population. Many offshore pelagic and deeper-water and mesopelagic species have few collection records, but are likely widespread in the region (often confirmed by deep ROV and submersible surveys), thus they are presumed to be residents. A few species are periodic residents, such as the Red-Shoulder Wrasse *Stethojulis bandanensis*, which can arrive in large numbers during the ENSO period and then subsequently dwindle and become rare (Victor et al. 2001).

We consider species that are limited to the Galapagos region as endemics, notwithstanding vagrant reports at adjacent areas. If there is a likely self-sustaining population of the species on any of the other offshore islands or mainland Ecuador or Peru (for cooler-water species), the species is not considered endemic to Galapagos. This definition reduces the endemism percentages cited in prior literature, some of which included “insular endemics” (to other offshore islands). Further reducing the endemism rate are some cooler-water fishes more recently found to be part of the mainland Ecuadorean and Peruvian fauna.

To clarify our criteria for inclusion, only species for which there are confirmed specimens in museums or diagnostic underwater or fresh photographs the authors have evaluated, are accepted for the list. Some uncertain identifications in museums have not yet been examined, but presently have no reason to be rejected, and they are included pending additional documentation. Isolated, juvenile, or solely photographic records of species outside their established ranges are subject to extra scrutiny before accepting their validity. Cases where there are observations only, even if by experienced observers, are not included, such as *Sphyrna mokarran*.

Due to the discovery of larvae of dozens of continental shorefish species in plankton-net collections from over the Rose Garden hydrothermal vents on the Galapagos Ridge (Victor, in press), a site on the EEZ boundary surrounding the archipelago (Fig. 1), records that are only from pelagic larvae or pelagic juveniles are not included. Another example, a giant larva (> 5cm) of the flatfish *Cyclosetta querna*, was recently photographed passing in the plankton at Kicker Rock, off Cristobal (Alex Hearn, pers. comm.), yet it is a soft-bottom species never recorded in Galapagos. Another example is the especially large larva of *Symphurus melanurus* (at 36.6 mm SL) collected within the EEZ in waters over the Galapagos Ridge. The species does not occur in Galapagos and Munroe & Krabbenhoft (2010) considered it an expatriated larva from a continental source, a similar situation to the large set of shorefish larvae advected from the continental coast documented in Victor (in press). In contrast, late larvae and juveniles collected at lights at night over inshore waters potentially would be considered valid records, since these fishes usually show signs of being in the process of settlement, or are local inshore pelagic species.

If there is a definite species entity present, documented, but only identifiable to genus, it is considered sp.; if a new species with a specimen confirmed by the authors to have diagnostic features and awaiting description, then it is n. sp. Suspected additional species without agreed-upon diagnostic characters and confirmed specimens are not included as “sp. A”, sp. B”, or “sp. 1”, despite being accepted in other published and unpublished species lists, due to the inevitable progressive inflation of species numbers by additional observers with varying degrees of expertise and confidence.

In addition to our own and colleagues’ observations, collections, DNA sequences, and photographs, we critically evaluate the published literature and online sources of museum records (www.gbif.org; www.obis.org; www.fishnet2.net; www.fishbase.net; www.vertnet.org); Eschmeyer’s Catalog of Fishes at <https://researcharchive>.

calacademy.org/research/ichthyology/catalog/fishcatmain.asp (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024); Robertson & Allen's (2024) guide Shorefishes of the Tropical Eastern Pacific (SFTEP) at <https://biogeodb.stri.si.edu/sftep/en/pages>; databases of DNA-sequence records (BOLD; www.boldsystems.org; GenBank: www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov); and online sources of photographic evidence, such as www.inaturalist.org, and a variety of commercial photography platforms.

Endemism

The Galapagos fish fauna has been of special interest for studies of endemism on isolated island groups, a key aspect of biogeography. A variety of features play a role in developing endemism among marine fishes, primarily the degree of isolation, by currents, delivery mechanisms, or distance from potential source populations, all interacting with the inherent dispersal ability of the species. Dispersal ability is affected by a number of factors, including whether eggs are benthic or released to be fertilized in the water column and subject to travel with currents. Among chondrichthyan fishes, there is internal fertilization and either benthic development in egg cases or birth of competent juveniles. In bony fishes, almost all species have larvae that become pelagic after the hatching of benthic eggs or broadcast spawning; a few release developed larvae who are subsequently pelagic, and some groups have eggs, larvae and juveniles that stay near the bottom without a pelagic stage and are limited to the continental margins. For pelagic stages, dispersal ability is determined by the maximum potential length of the pelagic larval or juvenile duration (with or without association with flotsam); and the swimming ability and behavior of pelagic stages (Leis 2015).

The rates of island endemism are calculated with varying numerators and denominators by various authors. Some are not strict on endemism, including offshore island endemics (insular endemics), i.e. those species that also occur on Cocos Island and/or Malpelo. On the other hand, one could allow any vagrant appearance of a Galapagos fish species at the mainland to end its endemic classification. The former inflates the rate of endemism and the latter not only reduces endemism rates, but makes the estimate unstable, as vagrants inevitably occur and the endemism percentage would decrease steadily over time.

TABLE A
Percentage endemic species for a variety of fish faunal categories
 (NUM is total count of species and END is the number of endemics in that category)

Category	code	ALL FISHES			Osteichthys			Chondrichthys			Chondrichthys + Myxiniformes		
		NUM	END	%	NUM	END	%	NUM	END	%	NUM	END	%
all fishes	total	683	67	9.8	614	52	8.5	60	7	11.7	68	15	22.1
all resident fishes	resident total	606	67	11.1	540	52	9.6	57	7	12.3	65	15	23.1
fishes (minus mesopelagics)	total-mid	572	67	11.7	503	52	10.3	60	7	11.7	68	15	22.1
resident fishes (minus mesopelagics)	res total-mid	495	67	13.5	429	52	12.1	57	7	12.3	65	15	23.1
shallow reef shorefishes	ss RV	325	36	11.1	319	36	11.3	7			7		
resident shallow reef shorefishes	ss res	260	36	13.8	254	36	14.2	7			7		
shallow inshore fishes *	ss np RV	353	36	10.2	347	36	10.4	7			7		
resident shallow inshore fishes	ss np res	283	36	12.7	277	36	13.0	7			7		
shallow fishes in & offshore	ss np op RV	449	36	8.0	413	36	8.73	35			35		
resident shallow fishes in & offshore	ss np op res	374	36	9.6	342	36	10.5	32			32		
shallow & deep inshore fishes	ss np d RV	476	67	14.1	436	52	11.9	31	7	22.6	39	15	38.5
resident shallow & deep inshorefishes	ss np d res	404	67	16.6	365	52	14.2	31	7	22.6	39	15	38.5

* shallow inshore fishes include shallow shorefishes plus nearshore pelagics (carangids & *Coryphaena*)

As for the denominator, there are many ways to add up the total fauna, and various authors use different sets of fishes, and sometimes unstated. If one includes vagrants, the rate of endemism decreases as new vagrant detections accumulate. Adding in offshore pelagic species, or especially the many mesopelagic fishes, also sharply reduces the estimate of endemism rate, since those categories contribute few to no endemic species.

Rather than pick a number, we have tried to apportion out the sources of variation and allow for more precise comparisons to other published endemism rates. We present the varying estimates in Table A. The overall rate of fish fauna endemism is around 10–15%; specifically 11.1% for shallow non-pelagic shorefishes (13.8% without vagrants). Most authors include nearshore pelagics with the shallow shorefishes, in that case the rate is 10.2% (12.7% without vagrants). Including deeper-water shorefishes, raises the rate to 14.1% (16.6% without vagrants). Adding in offshore pelagic groups along with shallow shorefishes drops the rate to 8.0% (9.6% without vagrants). The chondrichthyan fishes have a higher rate of endemism, up to 22.6% among inshore species, dropping in half when the many pelagic elasmobranchs are included. The set of 8 endemic hagfishes pushes the inshore non-osteichthyan endemism rate up to 38.5%.

Published rates of endemism for the Galapagos begin with Rosenblatt & Walker (1963), where they arrive at a particularly high 23% endemism of “shore fishes”, and then later in the article, 18% of “the species”. They do not explain what categories are included.

McCosker & Rosenblatt (1984) estimated 51 endemic species from the shorefish plus nearshore pelagic category, but said 7 are also at Cocos or Malpelo, leaving 44 out of 306 total or 14.38%. Their category is closest to our “shallow and deep inshore fishes” in Table A, which includes our nearshore pelagics, where we enumerate 67 endemics out of 476 species (including vagrants), with a quite similar rate of 14.1%.

Grove & Lavenberg (1997) make an estimate of 9.4% endemics (41 of 437 species) with a somewhat different combination of categories, but subtracting 13 species of flyingfishes in the denominator, the 9.7% approaches the broad estimate of 10% endemism.

McCosker (1998) updated his numbers to 73 true endemics of 526 species of the “ichthyofauna”, with no further categorization, yielding an estimate of 13.88% endemism (also unclear if vagrants are included and which non-reef species are included), and he then broadly estimates the endemism rate of the shorefishes as 14–16%.

McCosker & Rosenblatt (2010) update their estimates to 75 endemics (described as nearshore and deep slope) out of 550 species total (defined as all fishes not including mesopelagics) and calculate 13.6% endemism. Our matching estimate has fewer endemics at 67 from 572, yielding 11.7% endemism. They also calculate a category with 505 species total (excluding vagrants, mesopelagics, scombrids, echeneids, and exocoetids), and get 14.8% endemism. Our total excluding vagrants and mesopelagics is 494 species, and then excluding offshore pelagics, 403 species; if excluding offshore as only scombrids (10), echeneids (6), and exocoetids (10), we have 468 species with 14.3% endemism.

Tables

We present a variety of tables to optimize interpretations, for each species the family is also listed and then whether a resident, an endemic resident, or a vagrant:

Table 1 is the updated known species list in taxonomic order (following Catalog of Fishes order).

Table 2 is the same list in family alphabetical order.

Table 3 is the list of endemics (67 spp.).

Table 4 is the list of vagrants (76 spp.)

Table 5 begins with the practical species list for shallow resident shorefishes (260 spp.), then nearshore pelagics (28 spp.), these two groups comprise the species to be expected to be observed by scuba divers.

Table 6 is deepwater non-pelagic fishes (123 spp.),

Table 7 is offshore pelagic species (95 spp.),

Table 8 is mesopelagic species (111 spp.).

Table 9 is the table from Grove et al. (2022), retaining the original list on each original page, with bold font indicating added species (binomial), spelling corrections, changes in status, or updated taxonomy, and bold with a strike-through for species subtracted.

Notes on changes to the Grove et al. (2022) list

Additions or replacements

(Spelling corrections and simple species additions based on more recently reviewed museum records are not listed. Note that shallow-water rare or uncommon records are added as vagrants, while deeper-water fishes, typically difficult to survey or document, are usually considered residents.)

Branchiostomatidae is added since these cephalochordates are often included in lists of fishes and can be collected along with fishes along shallow shores.

Carcharodon carcharias is added to the list as a vagrant based on the recent documentation of a white shark at a fish aggregating device baited with sperm whale, adrift off Wolf, at the edge of the Marine Reserve, well within the EEZ (Salinas-de-León et al. 2024). A white shark had reportedly been observed underwater by Jonathan Green at Playa Escondida on Santa Fe in 1991, but no photographs were obtained to confirm the identification (Grove & Lavenberg 1997). In addition, a tooth morphologically matching *C. carcharias* was found by author JSG on a beach at Urvina Bay, Isabela (Todd & Grove 2010). The tooth bears signs of the type of erosion from rolling in sand, so it was either a naturally and recently-deposited shed tooth, or it possibly could have eroded out of earlier Holocene or Pleistocene sediments known from Isabela (the tooth currently cannot be located in the CDF collections).

Aetobatus ocellatus replaces *Aetobatus laticeps* based on a genetic study that found Galapagos specimens' sequences of cyt-b match the Indo-Pacific population of *A. ocellatus* and not the California type population of *A. laticeps* (Diana Pazmino, pers. comm). It may replace *A. laticeps* in Galapagos, Cocos, and Malpelo, however it is possible both species occur in the archipelago.

Hydrolagus melanopasma is added to the list based on a photograph obtained by author PSdL and it also appeared in recent video from an ROV in the “Hydrothermal Vents of the Western Galapagos” project.

Gymnothorax porphyreus is added to the list since it was recently photographed on Fernandina by author WBS, Carol Cox, and Frank Krasovec on the 2024 EPCA Foundation photographic survey. The species is found in Peru, but has not been seen previously or collected in Galapagos, despite the fact it is a large and distinctively marked moray, thus we consider it a vagrant. Described from the Juan Fernandez Islands off Chile, it is unclear which population of this complex is the true *G. porphyreus*: the mtDNA barcode database reveals that there is an Easter Island lineage 4% divergent from a Peruvian lineage (equidistant from the type location), with an additional New Zealand lineage about 3% away (also labeled *G. porphyreus*). Thus the Peruvian lineage, nearest to Galapagos, may or may not represent true *G. porphyreus*.

Bascanichthys bascanoides is added since it was recently photographed by Carlos Estape at Floreana on the 2024 EPCA Foundation photographic survey. This genus of snake eel typically buries in sand and they are rarely observed even when common (e.g. off Florida), thus a photograph in Galapagos likely means a resident population.

Bathytroctes macrolepis is added due to the record MCZ 50743, within the EEZ, of *Bathytroctes alvifrons* Garman, 1899, now considered a junior synonym of *B. macrolepis*; it replaces *B. microlepis* which is also present in the TEP (Robertson et al. 2017) but not confirmed in the Galapagos.

Maurollicus breviculus Parin & Kobylansky, 1993, described from the open ocean midway between Galapagos and Ecuador, falls within a widespread Indo-Pacific clade 4C when DNA-sequenced in the phylogenetic study by Rees et al. (2020). The clade contains a set of species likely oversplit taxonomically, and accordingly it is synonymized with *M. australis* Hector, 1875 (described from New Zealand, and the senior synonym), along with Chilean *M. parvipinnis* Vaillant, 1888; Japanese *M. japonicus* Ishikawa, 1915; and South African *M. walvisensis* Parin & Kobylansky, 1993. *M. australis* replaces the record of *M. amethystinopunctatus*, which is an Atlantic species and in a different clade.

Astronesthes galapagensis Parin, Borodulina & Hulley, 1999 replaces *A. boulengerie* Gilchrist, 1982, described as the TEP sister species of from South Africa. Four additional *Astronesthes* species occur in waters around Galapagos and are added to the list (Parin & Borodulina 2003), replacing *A. martensii* which is from the Indian Ocean.

Aulopus chirichignoae was described recently from Peru (Bearez et al. 2024) and replaces the listing of the northern sister species, *A. bajacali* from Baja California. The mtDNA sequence from SIO 02-68 from the Paramount Seamounts near Galapagos (GenBank EU366559) matches the Peruvian sequences, and that lineage is 2.65% from the Baja California lineage of *A. bajacali*.

Desmodema polystictum is added to the list, identified from a recent photograph of the characteristic polka-dotted juvenile at Isabela in 2021 by Carlos Palma, referred by Alex Hearn.

Regalecus russellii is added to the list, identified from a 2022 video referred by Alex Hearn, from fishermen off Santiago showing a giant oarfish on the boat, with the diagnostic features of a length of about 3 m, a mostly uniform body width, and rounded spots.

Cataetyx rubirostris Gilbert, 1890, known from Oregon to Chile, is added to the list based on SIO 90-69 from the Galapagos, the taxonomic status of the specimen needs to be confirmed.

Paracaristius sp. is added here for juvenile records of this genus in the region since recent reports indicate that both *P. nudarcus* and *P. maderensis* are present in the TEP, and identifications from juveniles are difficult (Angulo et al. 2014).

Evorthodus minutus, a brackish and freshwater goby from the continental coastline, is added to the list as a vagrant based on a single adult collected from a tidepool in Academy Bay, Santa Cruz, during the Templeton Crocker Expedition in 1932 (Valencia-Mendez, Catania & López-Pérez 2019). Although they discussed stepping-stone travel from island to island and ballast water as dispersal mechanisms, Victor (in press) collected and mtDNA-sequenced numerous pelagic larvae of continental brackish and freshwater gobioids at a site over the Galapagos Ridge near the EEZ boundary, including *Evorthodus minutus*, *Erotelis armiger*, *Gobiomorus maculatus*, and *Sicydium* spp., all presumably being advected from the Central American coastline.

Sphyraena stellata was recently described by Morishita & Motomura (2020) as the striped barracuda from the central Pacific; on the list it replaces *S. helleri*, the relative that is endemic to Hawaii. A population of *S. stellata* apparently occurs infrequently in Galapagos, where they have been photographed over multiple years at Wolf (a video transect in 2015 and recently by author WBS), as well as at Baltra (iNaturalist photograph). The identification is based on the similar appearance, i.e. a blue upper midlateral stripe overlying yellow and/or darker stripes along the flanks. Note that the local *S. idiaestes* has a yellow stripe, but it is midlateral, brighter anteriorly where it extends onto the head, and not accompanied by dark stripes on the flanks (also note juveniles of all barracudas can have dark stripes). Despite being infrequently encountered, photographs and videos show these barracudas swimming in schools, thus qualifying the population in the archipelago as resident (Mossbrucker et al. 2023).

Polydactylus approximans is added since it does reach the archipelago as vagrants on occasion. Two adults have been collected, both on Santa Cruz, CDRS 11459 in 1963 and CDRS 10711 in 2012. Two older records, at both SIO and LACM, refer to samples brought to the museum(s) by J. Mershon, who spent time on a tuna clipper between the continent and Galapagos, thus the provenance of the fish is not known. A 15-mm pelagic juvenile of this species was collected and mtDNA-sequenced from a site over the Galapagos Ridge (Victor, in press).

Decapterus macarellus is added based on recent photographs by Allison Morgan Estape and Carlos J. Estape on Pinta during the 2024 EPCA Foundation photographic survey showing the diagnostic all-yellow tail and mid-lateral bright blue stripe. The species is found worldwide in tropical and subtropical oceans and thus would be expected in Galapagos as well.

Scartichthys gigas is added as a vagrant since it has been observed sporadically in Galapagos, with a photograph from San Cristobal in the first edition of the guide by Humann & DeLoach (1993) labeled as the Blackstriped Blenny “a possibly undescribed species”, but left out of the later edition. Author WBS has also photographed the species on Floreana. The species is a vagrant arriving from its native range in Peru and Chile.

Lutjanus colorado is added as a vagrant based on a photograph of a single adult from the mangroves on Isabela

in 2014 by David Acuña-Marrero (Mossbrucker et al. 2023).

Diplectrum spp. have been documented in Galapagos, in small numbers, under a variety of names and with an abundance of confusion. Only two species are confirmed. One is added to the list, *Diplectrum rostrum*, from Tagus Cove (FMNH 41433), it was identified in the review of the genus by Bortone (1977). In addition, the mtDNA barcode of a specimen collected by BCV from Tagus Cove in June 1999 matched *D. rostrum* from Baja California. Interestingly, the only place *Diplectrum* were found in the EPCA Foundation photographic survey was also Tagus Cove, and there were several documented. The second species is a single record of two small *Diplectrum eumelum*, confirmed by BCV in SIO 15-1254: with no apparent resident population, it is included in the list as vagrant. The other species that have been listed for Galapagos are removed from the list, see below under subtractions.

Sebastobus altivelis is added to the list based on a photograph of a deep scorpionfish at the Paramount Seamount along the Cocos Ridge (within the Ecuadorean EEZ) from the NOAA Galápagos Rift Expedition in 2011. This temperate-zone genus has only recently been documented in the TEP, when Robertson et al. (2017) collected a specimen off Costa Rica, extending the known range southwards by almost 3,000 km. That specimen was DNA-barcoded and it matched to the lineage of *Sebastobus altivelis* from California. Based on that, we assign the species photographed at Paramount Seamount to *S. altivelis*. We consider it a resident since these deepwater scorpionfish are difficult to find and recognize and likely occur more widely.

Kyphosus cinerascens is added to the list as a vagrant based on a recent photograph by Carlos Estape from Wolf. The identification is confirmed by Kendall Clements (pers. comm.).

Kyphosus sectatrix is added to the list as a resident based on a series of recent photographs by WBS from Floreana, Darwin (as a partial xanthic morph) and three individuals together at Marchena; by Allison M. Estape at Floreana and Baltra; the identifications are confirmed by Kendall Clements (pers. comm.). Since few people are able to identify these species, they are likely well undercounted.

Lobotes pacifica is added to the list as a vagrant based on a recent photograph by David Acuña-Marrero of adults at a buoy at Wolf (Mossbrucker et al. 2023).

Naso hexacanthus is added to the list as a vagrant based on a recent photograph from Floreana; author IK notes the species has been observed previously at Darwin and Floreana during ENSO periods.

Lactoria diaphana is added to the list as a vagrant based on a single 82-mm specimen collected at a nightlight in Tagus Cove in 1967 (SIO 15-2501). This species is exceptional in that adults can be pelagic and most specimens are collected in offshore waters or from stomachs of pelagic predators. While frequent in the northern part of the TEP, this is the only specimen from Galapagos or the wider central or southern TEP.

Aluterus monoceros is added to the list as a vagrant based on recent photographs from Genovesa by Greg Estes (pers. comm.) and from Bartolome by Sylvain Le Bris on iNaturalist.

Subtractions

Sphyrna mokarran may have been seen once underwater, by Robert Lavenberg (Grove & Lavenberg 1997), however no photographs were taken and no other divers at the time made a similar observation, nor have there been any observations since. It is removed from the list.

Sphyrna tiburo has been previously listed as a Galapagos species, however, we have found no current or historical evidence of the species in the Galapagos and it is removed from the list. A recent genetic study (Aroca, Tavera & Torres 2022) resurrected the name *Sphyrna vespertina*, previously considered an eastern Pacific subspecies of *S. tiburo*. The COI mtDNA sequence of a Peruvian *S. vespertina* is 1.16% divergent from Atlantic *S. tiburo*.

Chimaera sp. is removed from the list, there are no records or photographs.

Bathycongrus n. sp. is removed from the list; it has been proposed, but does not have diagnostic criteria at present.

Chiloconger dentatus (Garman, 1899) has been collected as leptocephalus larvae over the Galapagos Ridge and DNA-barcoded (Victor, in press); there were 20 larvae 43–158 mm SL, but no benthic specimens have been collected within the EEZ. The species is removed from the list, even though it is very likely to be found in deepwater collections or videos.

Gnathophis cinctus (Garman, 1899) has not been identified from any non-larval specimen in the area, and therefore

is removed from the list, even though it is very likely to be found in deepwater collections or videos. Notably, the holotype of the species is a leptocephalus larva (MCZ 28428) collected by Garman in the Galapagos near Marchena, described as *Atopichthys cinctus*, but no benthic specimen has been forthcoming. Additional leptocephali have been collected since within the EEZ (SIO 55-234 and 72-39).

Japanoconger n. sp. is removed from the list; it has been proposed, but does not have diagnostic criteria at present. *Bregmaceros maclellandi* Thompson, 1840 (often misspelled) is removed from the list since it is now considered limited to the Indian Ocean (Anderson 2022). *Bregmaceros bathymaster* Jordan & Bollman, 1890 is described from the TEP while *B. longipes* Garman, 1899, also from the TEP, is designated a junior synonym (Torii, Harold & Ozawa 2003). Harold & Baltzegar (2023) also examined *B. atlanticus* specimens from the TEP (and described *Bregmaceros moseri* from Hawaii and the South Pacific Gyre and perhaps the California Current). However, there are only two records of *Bregmaceros* from Galapagos, and neither has been identified to species (MCZ 33059 as “*B. nectabanus*” and CAS 46082 as “sp.”), leaving *B. bathymaster* the putative species and likely a vagrant arrival.

Merluccius angustimanus occurs along the continental margin from Baja California to Colombia, while *Merluccius gayi* is described from Chile, and reported from coastal Ecuador and Peru; it is arguably distinct from *M. angustimanus* (Pérez et al. 2021). We remove *M. gayi* from the list since no apparent record can be found for the genus in Galapagos. The species was said to be “uncommonly seen” in Grove & Lavenberg (1997) and is listed in McCosker & Rosenblatt (2010), with no evidence. Similarly, Arturo Angulo (pers. comm.) reports that no records at UCR are from Cocos Island, only from the mainland (e.g. Bussing & Lopez’s (2004) listing of UCR 1243-1). Lloris, Matallanas & Oliver (2005) do not extend any of the species to any offshore islands of the TEP in their book “Hakes of the World”.

Porichthys margaritatus is removed from the list even though it has been included in the Galapagos fauna in all prior listings, however there are no records after 1929. But, as toadfishes, *Porichthys* do not have pelagic larvae, and therefore do not occur on any (other) off-shelf islands anywhere in the New World (Robertson & Van Tassell 2023, Robertson & Allen 2024); even a Hawaiian record (MHNH 1896-0178) is also a location error. There are numerous apparent errors in the catalogs that suggest the species was not in Galapagos. Multiple records are from the 1888 *Albatross* Expedition, but always missing a date (most other records of continental *Porichthys* from the expedition have dates). The first error is the record of *Porichthys “nautopedium”* CAS (SU) 227 (5 fish, no date) that says “paratype”, but the description of *P. nautopedium* (now a junior synonym) in Jordan & Bollman (1890; p. 171 & 172) says the new species was collected “off coast of Colombia” at stations 2795 & 2802 and those are in the Gulf of Panama (Colombia in 1890). Additional collections labeled Galapagos are CAS (SU) 5849 & 5850 (9 fish with no date) and USNM 41161 (2 fish with no date, no station, and notably all adjacent accession numbers are *Albatross* collections from Panama). In the species list at the end of the article, Jordan & Bollman (1890; p. 182) have “Indefatigable” along with the collection station numbers that are all Panama (perhaps a slip-up since the line right after the range sentence of *P. nautopedium* is the name *O. indefatigabile*). Another old record, of *Porichthys “notatus”* CAS (SU) 54413, is listed as from Eden Island, Galapagos, on 13 January 1929 during the Herre Expedition; however Herre’s complete list of fishes they collected (Herre 1936, p. 13 & 14) does not include the *Porichthys*. Finally, an additional catalog record, USNM 305007, with 27 fish, from 3 April 1967, has apparently erroneous coordinates of 4.65°, -109.4°, well out into the open ocean west of Galapagos, but that was from a Puerto Rican AEC Laboratory expedition and it was surveying the Bay of Panama in that month, and on 4 April 1967, the next day, they collected at the mouth of the Sabana River in the Bay of Panama (USNM 303234).

Thunnus alalunga, the Albacore Tuna, is a more temperate species usually found above and below 10° latitude. Records get confused since the common name is frequently confounded with *Thunnus albacares*, the ubiquitous Yellowfin Tuna. Although the IATCC illustrates the species from the general area, no specific or unequivocal record of *T. alalunga* can be traced to Galapagos waters and it is removed from the list.

Bollmannia is removed from the list since it does not occur in Galapagos. The records of *B. macropoma* are a product of an erroneous identification by Bedenbaugh (1988, p. 19: as from “Galapagos. Punta Arenas: CAS 3559 (1; 62.0)”) of a specimen of *Dialommus fuscus*, listed in CAS 3559. It was collected by the Templeton-

Crocker Expedition at Santa Cruz in Galapagos, and identified as *Crockeridius odysseus* Clark, 1936 (a junior synonym of *D. fuscus*). Similarly, Bedenbough (1988, p. 26) erroneously lists *B. umbrosus* as from “Galapagos. Port Angeles Light: CAS 4733 (1; 44.5). Santa Maria Bay: CAS 2685 (1; 69.2)”; however, the former collection in the catalog is from Oaxaca and the latter from Sinaloa, both Mexico.

Nematistius pectoralis is listed in the Crane Expedition fishes by Herre (1936) who reported “a number of large specimens” caught line fishing in Tagus Cove, Isabela. However, we remove the species from the list since those specimens were not retained and there are no known photographs or museum specimens. Fernando Rivera (pers. comm.) reports that over many years he has seen none brought in by fishermen.

Remora australis is removed from the list since there are no known photographs or specimens.

Cypselurus angusticeps is removed from the Galapagos list following the most recent review by Shakhovskoy & Parin (2024) which considers *C. angusticeps* in the TEP to be limited to a northern range, extending south only to about 14° N. They do not accept the old map sector listed for the species in Parin et al. (1990; south of the Galapagos, one degree square 4–5° S, 88–89° W), with no specimen known, noting that Parin did not include that record in his subsequently reviews of the flyingfishes.

Hirundichthys rondeletii (Valenciennes, 1847) is considered a worldwide species complex, with the type population limited to the Mediterranean and Atlantic, and thus removed from the list. Parin & Belyanina (2002) split the subtropical complex with *H. rufipinnis* (Valenciennes, 1847) in the subtropical southern Pacific to Peru and Chile and *H. gilberti* (Snyder, 1904) from Japan, Hawaii, and across to the California Current. The tropical range between those two is filled by *H. marginatus* (Nichols & Breder, 1928), which is not a member of the complex: mtDNA sequences shows it closer to the *H. affinis* and *H. speculiger* clade than to *H. rondeletii* and *H. rufipinnis* (Lewallen 2019). A second TEP congener, *H. speculiger*, is a circumglobal species widely distributed in the Pacific (Shakhovskoy 2018). There are a couple of *H. albimaculatus* records, but well south of Galapagos, that may represent vagrants from the central Pacific range for the species (Parin & Belyanina 2002).

Parexocoetus brachypterus is removed from list since Parin et al. (1990) do not record the species at or below the equator, and Parin (1995) illustrates the species as neritic along the continental shelf from Panama to Ecuador. Note that juveniles of other genera can have a “*Parexocoetus*-stage” which can lead to potential misidentifications (Shakhovskoy & Parin 2024).

Prognichthys spp. are removed from the list since collection records concentrate north of Galapagos and exclude the area around Galapagos and southwards; Parin et al. (1990) do not record either regional species of *Prognichthys* at or below the equator. Parin (1995) has the shading for the vast Pacific range of *P. sealei* ending about at Galapagos, but with no collection records, and his *P. tringa* range is limited to the neritic zone along the continent. Ilya Shakhovskoy (pers. comm.) recommends species identifications not be made from photographs of flyingfishes. In his review of species ranges he specifically “refused to use literature data and data from databases of the internet due to a large number of misidentifications of flying fish species” (Shakhovskoy 2018).

Ekemblemaria sp. has been on Galapagos species lists for many years, however it was based on an underwater observation of a shallow, hole-dwelling blennioid fish on Plazas Islands by John McCosker in 1977 who considered it an undescribed species of *Ekemblemaria* (McCosker, Taylor & Warner 1978). He relates “I saw three or four in the worm tubes attached to that rock. But that’s all that I saw after numerous searches at that and other similar locations.. and tried numerous times to collect it. I never succeeded. David Doubilet photographed it with its fin extended outside of the worm tube” (John McCosker, pers. comm., 6 August 2022). David Doubilet’s photograph has been lost to follow up with no photograph resulting from contacts with him. Given that no additional encounters have occurred over many years, the existence of the entity cannot be confirmed and it is removed from the list (note that the color image 112 in Grove & Lavenberg (1997) of a blenny with a blue-spotted head is likely a juvenile *Acanthemblemaria castroi*).

Cookeolus japonicus is removed from the list since there are no known photographs or specimens.

Cilus gilberti and *Cynoscion phoxocephalus* are removed from the list since they are continental sciaenids with the only records being SIO collections donated by fishermen on tuna clippers fishing between the mainland and the islands, and including species from both locations (and often also with multiple species from the

continent, e.g. of *Macrodon*, *Nebris*, *Sciaena*, *Larimus*): i.e. SIO 50-292 (with 5 species of sciaenids), SIO 54-174, and SIO 79-51). A photograph of a 2-cm juvenile sciaenid from Galapagos (we have not seen) cannot be identified with any certainty (Grove & Lavenberg 1997).

Mycteroperca xenarcha Jordan, 1888 is removed from the list, even though it was described from a type specimen putatively from Galapagos (MCZ 24198), collected on the 1872 Hassler Expedition, which also collected in Peru after departing the Galapagos. In the same Galapagos collection, there are specimens also called *M. olfax*, and in the Peruvian collections the next month there are specimens called both species. However, no *M. olfax* has been collected in Peru since 1872, and no *M. xenarcha* has been seen in Galapagos since then. There are many inconsistencies in the collection data from MCZ records: among others, the species is described from a “seven inch” specimen and the present holotype is 365 mm SL; notes say specimens have been removed from jars and renumbered; written catalog entries do not match other data for the specimen(s) (e.g. MCZ 10223 lists 4 specimens of *M. olfax* from Peru); and Jordan (1888, p. 387) writes “several specimens of this species from the Galapagos Islands are in the [MCZ], these were mixed with specimens of the more common *Mycteroperca olfax*, from the same locality.” However, no other *M. xenarcha* are recorded from Galapagos, and their finding multiple specimens in Galapagos argues persuasively that fishes on the expedition had been mislabeled, at the time and/or subsequently at museums.

Diplectrum spp. have been documented in Galapagos, but only two species are confirmed (see above under additions). All other species are not confirmed; the easiest to discard are the records from SIO collections derived from ships in transit that combine shorefishes from Peru or Panama along with Galapagos species (SIO 50-292 listing *Diplectrum pacificum* and SIO 79-51 listing *Diplectrum maximum*). Furthermore, small juveniles should not be able to be identified to species, indeed, juvenile records examined by BCV proved to be *Serranus psittacinus*, an abundant species with a midlateral stripe superficially similar to *Diplectrum* (i.e. USNM 321375, LACM 45634-20, and LACM 45654-1). The FMNH 41433 *D. rostrum* is labeled in databases as *D. pacificum*, the name assigned prior to the description of *D. rostrum* in 1974; a photograph of the museum specimen is easily confirmed as *D. rostrum* by BCV. Bortone’s review of the genus concluded there are 4 species in the Galapagos, but he (and others) includes *Diplectrum euryplectrum* on a misreading of the type location of the species, it is not Galapagos but Panama (Jordan & Bollman 1880, pp. 157, 158, 181). He also includes *Diplectrum macropoma* based solely on CAS 1569, however that specimen is also from the *Albatross* collection, and Jordan & Bollman (1880, pp. 157) in their enumeration of that *Albatross* collection show *D. macropoma* as only collected from Panama. Note that the locations are errors or suspect for a series of CAS records of *Albatross* specimens listed as “Galapagos” (e.g. CAS 10348, 10793–10800), likely someone assuming all expedition records were specifically from Galapagos.

Paralabrax humeralis is removed from the list since there are no confirmed photographs or specimens; the species is limited to Peru and Chile (Hildebrand 1946, Daniel Pondella, pers. comm.) and not included in modern Galapagos listings, where the endemic *P. albomaculatus* is the only accepted species (Grove & Lavenberg 1997, McCosker & Rosenblatt 2010, Robertson & Allen 2024). There are a series of listings more than 70 years old, many from Tagus Cove (where *P. albomaculatus* are frequently encountered). It appears that early surveys called the native *P. albomaculatus* as *P. humeralis*, to wit Seale (1940) listed only *P. humeralis* from the Allan Hancock collections adding that they were “the common seabass of the Galapagos” and “easily distinguished by the row of large white blotches”, i.e. *P. albomaculatus*.

Peristedion barbiger Garman, 1899 is removed from the list since there is a single Galapagos record, from the 1905 *Albatross* collection from off Espanola (CAS 35299), while all subsequent collections are *Peristedion crustosum* Garman, 1899, including several recent submersible specimens (some from near the old *Albatross* locality). According to Richards & McCosker (1998), the only *Peristedion* in Galapagos is *P. crustosum*. The fish in CAS 35299 are presently missing from the collection (Jon Fong, pers. comm.).

Pontinus sp. A, B and C are removed from the list; they were listed by McCosker & Rosenblatt (2010) without diagnostic criteria (there is no indication they meant sp. A to correspond to *Pontinus* sp. A (Rosy) documented by Robertson et al. (2017) off Panama, Costa Rica, Nicaragua, and El Salvador). They add that those three unknown species they have observed deep in Galapagos are in addition to *Pontinus clemensi* (the common “brujo” providing much of the fishery catch in the archipelago), *Pontinus strigatus*, and one new observation

of *Pontinus vaughani*.

Pontinus vaughani is removed from the list since we have not seen photographs or specimens of that northern species in Galapagos (it is found from Baja California south to Clipperton). McCosker & Rosenblatt (2010) report a single photograph was taken, but we have not yet been able to confirm it.

Pontinus strigatus Heller & Snodgrass, 1903 was described from a single small specimen taken from the stomach of a shark off Wolf. Notably, the authors did not compare the specimen to *Pontinus furcirhinus* Garman, 1899, described a few years before from large series of specimens off Panama and Colombia. The small holotype shares the elongated third dorsal-fin spine diagnostic of *P. furcirhinus* and has no features that differentiate it from small *P. furcirhinus*. Furthermore, underwater videos and photographs show that *P. furcirhinus* is one of the most common fishes observed below 100 m around Galapagos, and the second most frequent *Pontinus* landed in the fishery at Puerto Ayora (locally called “brujo de lomo negro”; Carlos J. Estape, pers. comm.). A third and smaller species of *Pontinus* can be seen in photographs of heaps of *Pontinus* landed at Puerto Ayora; it has short dorsal-fin spines and no obvious spotting, features which fit the widespread *Pontinus sierra* in the region. *Pontinus* larvae were collected in large numbers over the hydrothermal vents at the EEZ boundary, including *P. furcirhinus* and *P. sierra* (with DNA barcodes). We thus can confirm three species in Galapagos: *P. clemensi*, *P. furcirhinus*, and *P. sierra*, and any others await additional observations and/or photographs.

Abantennarius coccineus is removed from the list since there are no confirmed photographs or specimens. McCosker (1998), in his book review of Grove & Lavenberg (1997), reports a photograph by Paul Humann is the only Galapagos record for *A. coccineus*, and refers to Robert Myers as the source, but Myers does not have any information on that (pers. comm.). Ted Pietsch (pers. comm.) cited McCosker & Rosenblatt’s (2010) listing, but he has not found any specimens from Galapagos; he adds that no photographs in the Humann guides are *A. coccineus*.

Mola mola is removed from the list since there are no confirmed photographs or specimens. A genetic study found all the *Mola* sampled in Galapagos (but that was 9 fish from Punta Vicente Roca) proved to be *Mola alexandrini* (Thys et al. 2014; as “*M. ramsayi*”), now listed as a resident. Until evidence is obtained, we do not confirm the presence of *M. mola*. While considered the southern species, *M. alexandrini* can be found in some northern locations and both species are documented in South Africa (Thys et al. 2014).

Ranzania laevis is removed from the list since there are no known photographs or specimens.

Taxonomic name changes

Stomias atriventer Garman, 1899 is elevated from the TEP subspecies of widespread *S. boa* found throughout the remaining Indo-Pacific (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024).

Scopelogadus bispinosus was considered a subspecies of *S. mizolepis*: Kotlyar (2021) elevated the TEP population to species status.

Carapinae is now classified as a sub-family of Ophidiidae (replacing Carapidae) after recent phylogenetic studies (Betancur et al. 2017).

Ophidion sp. A, a long-standing entity listed in Galapagos was recently described as *Ophidion galapagensis* by Lea & Robins (2024).

Cataetyx simus (Garman, 1899) includes a syntype from within the EEZ (MCZ 28633). Note the family listed for this species is corrected from Ophidiidae to Bythitidae.

Aphanopus capricornis is known in the TEP from a single Galapagos specimen (CAS 86497) collected during a volcanic eruption at Fernandina (McCosker et al. 1997), initially listed as *A. intermedius*, an Atlantic species, later corrected to *A. capricornis* in McCosker & Rosenblatt (2010).

Trichiurus nitens Garman, 1899 is the sole member of the genus described from the TEP (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024), the mtDNA barcode lineage is about 2% divergent from multiple lineages for the widespread Atlantic and Indo-West Pacific populations of nominal *T. lepturus*.

Cosmocampus coccineus (Herald, 1940), described from the Galapagos, is elevated by Hamilton et al. (2016) from a subspecies of *Cosmocampus arctus* (Jenkins & Evermann, 1889) which was described from the Sea

of Cortez.

Doryrhamphus melanopleura is the Pacific Ocean sister species to Indian Ocean *D. excisus*, and the TEP population is presently considered *D. melanopleura* (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024); however the barcode mtDNA sequence of a fish from Galapagos is 2.3% divergent from *D. melanopleura* in French Polynesia.

Microdesminae is now classified as a subfamily of Gobiidae (replacing Microdesmidae) after recent phylogenetic studies (Nelson, Grande & Wilson 2016, Betancur et al. 2017).

Schindleria praematura is now classified in a subfamily of Gobiidae (replacing Schindleriidae) after recent phylogenetic studies (Nelson, Grande & Wilson 2016, Betancur et al. 2017).

Oligoplites inornatus Gill, 1863 is elevated from a subspecies of *Oligoplites saurus* (Bloch & Schneider, 1801), originally described from the Caribbean (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024).

Platybelone argalus pterura (Osborne & Nichols, 1916) is now listed as a subspecies of *P. argalus* (Lesueur, 1821), a circumglobal single species complex. It is a subjective decision (given the ambiguity of subspecies), but since the putative vicariant event is more likely isolation from the central Pacific Ocean and not from the rise of the Panama isthmus, the potential for gene flow across the East Pacific Barrier has not been assessed. At present, the mtDNA sequence for TEP *P. argalus pterura* is only 0.9% divergent from Indo-Pacific and Atlantic subspecies of *P. argalus*, but that is based on a single TEP sequence and additional specimens may well unite the lineages and bring into question the status of the sub-population.

Hemilutjanus macrophthalmus has long had an unresolved phylogenetic placement and classification. Smith et al. (2022) recently used molecular phylogenetic analyses to conclude that it is an acropomatiform taxon most fitting the family Malakichthyidae.

Anisotremus scapularis replaces *Genyatremus scapularis* since phylogenetic studies show the species is closely related to other *Anisotremus* species (Tavera et al. 2014).

Epinephelidae, Liopropomatidae, Grammistidae, and Anthiadidae have been recently elevated to families after traditionally being considered as subfamilies of Serranidae (Near & Thacker 2024). Ma & Craig (2018) justify the family status of Epinephelidae.

Cephalopholis colonus replaces *Epinephelus colonus* or *Paranthias colonus* since phylogenetic studies show the species is closely related to other *Cephalopholis* species within the family Epinephelidae (Ma & Craig 2018).

Bodianus darwini replaces *Semicossyphus darwini* since phylogenetic studies show *Semicossyphus* is within a broad *Bodianus* clade (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024).

Trachyscorpia was assigned to Sebastidae, however Sebastinae and Setarchinae have been determined to be subfamilies of Scorpaenidae after recent phylogenetic studies (Nelson, Grande & Wilson 2016, Betancur et al. 2017).

Epigonus merleni is replaced by *Epigonus macrops* since a reexamination by Okamoto, Bartsch & Motomura (2012) of the unique holotype skimmed from the surface during the underwater eruption of Isla Fernandina (McCosker et al. 1995, McCosker & Long 1997) found it to be a junior synonym of *E. macrops*, a circumglobal species originally described from Sumatra.

Changes in endemic status

Myxinidae: the 8 recently described hagfish species (Mincarone et al. 2021) are considered endemic since their depth ranges are on the upper slope (not abyssal), promoting isolation. Reproduction by benthic eggs would also reduce dispersal, and thus far the species have only been found on Galapagos. Nevertheless, hagfishes are poorly documented in the region and some or all of these species may prove to be more widespread.

Bythaelurus giddingsi, *Apristurus* n. sp., *Galeus* n. sp., and *Rajella eisenhardti* are all now considered endemic species since no confirmed records exist outside the Galapagos Archipelago.

Hydrolagus alphus, *Hydrolagus mccoskeri*, and *Hydrolagus* n. sp. are all now considered endemic species since no confirmed records exist outside the Galapagos Archipelago.

Calamus taurinus (Jenyns, 1840) is now considered an endemic since it was described from Galapagos, but without clear distinguishing features from *Calamus brachysomus* (Lockington, 1880), described from Baja

California, it may be that it is the senior synonym for populations outside the Galapagos as well.

Umbrina galapagorum is returned to endemic status since it was not recognized due to a single record from Cocos Island at of 11 fish from the 1891 *Albatross* expedition (MCZ 30796). However, all subsequent collections, from the very limited beach area on the island, by seining shallows or poisoning the freshwater outflow at Wafer Bay, caught large numbers of *Umbrina xanti* (38 from SIO 77-89; 40 from LACM 35473.007; UBC 540402; AMNH I-8528). We presume the same fish collected in the same very restricted habitat on the island are the same species.

Larimus pacificus is changed to vagrant based on the single adult specimen collected by John McCosker in Academy Bay, Santa Cruz (CAS 54887). Only one other record exists (LACM 44086), from a local fisherman with no provenance.

Idiastion hageyi McCosker, 2008 and *Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri* Wiboro & Motomura, 2017 are changed to endemic, since they are described from unique holotypes collected from a submersible: the former from a single specimen off Fernandina (at 522 m) and the latter from a single collection off Darwin (at 515 m). However, underwater videos from elsewhere in the region show scorpionfishes that fit the descriptions, but are not confirmed as either species. It is very likely they are both found outside the Galapagos.

Paraliparis darwini Stein & Chernova, 2002 and *Paraliparis galapagosensis* Stein & Chernova, 2002 are changed to endemic, since they are described from unique holotypes collected from a submersible.

Changes in resident status

Aetomyleus asperrimus is changed to a vagrant since only a single museum record exists from Galapagos: FMNH 41572, collected in 1941 at Elizabeth Bay in Isabela.

Mobula thurstoni is changed to a resident since individuals and schools have been photographed at multiple locations in the archipelago (Mossbrucker et al. 2023), and at Floreana by Serenity Mitchell, and Santa Cruz and Cousin's Rock by Carlos J. Estape on the 2024 EPCA Foundation photographic survey.

Gymnothorax buroensis is an Indo-Pacific moray, changed to a vagrant since there are only three known museum specimens and no photographs. The collections are quite old, from the *Velero III* in 1932 and 1933 (LACM 45664.002 & 45620.003 and one from 1968 at SIO 74-103).

Phaenomonas pinnata was listed as a vagrant, however this genus of snake eel typically buries in sand and they are very rarely observed or collected within their known range; two were collected in Floreana in SIO 12-3083, causing a change to resident status.

Fistularia corneta is changed to a vagrant since only a single record exists from Galapagos, a juvenile 198 mm SL from a nightlight collection on Isabela (SIO 63-73).

Microdesmus dipus Gunther, 1864 is changed to a vagrant since it is known from a single individual described as the new species *Microdesmus reidi* Myers & Wade, 1946 collected from a tidepool at Darwin Bay, Genovesa on the *Velero III* Allan Hancock Foundation Expedition in 1938 (LACM 21031). Dawson (1968) did not mention this species when he reviewed *M. dipus*. The specimen does not match the meristics (51 dorsal-fin elements while *M. dipus* ranges from 53–58 among a notably large sample of 175 individuals examined by Dawson). Furthermore, *M. reidi* was a relatively large adult, 67.5 mm SL, documented in life to be translucent yellowish-gray, and “the only real color” a pink belly, while *M. dipus* has complex dark blotches and bars on the head and body (and most adult specimens were smaller than 67 mm SL). The species identification is thus tentative.

Tylosurus fodiator is changed to a vagrant since there are apparently only two records: a one-meter specimen collected by Fiddi Angermeyer in 1984 at Marchena (LACM 43663-1) and one by John McCosker from Bartolome in 1998 (USNM 352054). The species is large, conspicuous, and easy to catch on hook and line, so very unlikely to escape detection. All other *Tylosurus* records from Galapagos are apparently *Strongylura exilis* under various synonyms, including *Tylosurus exilis*, *T. stolzmanni* (Jordan & Bollman 1890), and *T. scapularis*.

Tylosurus pacificus (Steindachner, 1875) is changed to a vagrant since Collette & Banford (2001) report a

single specimen from Galapagos collected by the Fifth Vanderbilt Expedition; it was originally described as *Strongylura galapagensis* Fowler, 1944 (now a junior synonym). The close (about 1% divergent) sister species *Tylosurus melanotus* is also present in the TEP (often as *T. acus melanotus*, a subspecies of a circumtropical *T. acus*, but there is a 3% divergence in mtDNA from Caribbean *T. acus* to TEP *T. melanotus*). Collette & Banford (2001) noted *T. pacificus* co-occurs with *T. melanotus* in the region.

Xenichthys xanti has few records in the archipelago, all but one from before about 70 years ago (MCZ 25578, CAS 3881, 3882, 3883, 24414, FMNH 22625, CMNFI 1968-0592.14; and recent LACM 45588-7 from author JSG) and some are questionable, we list it as vagrant until specimens can be confirmed. The distinction from endemic *Xenichthys agassizii* can be difficult.

Epinephelus analogus has always been considered present at Galapagos, since it was listed in Jordan & Bollman (1880, p. 181) as collected at Floreana. However, at present the only *Albatross* specimens at CAS are from Panama (CAS 381 & 3807). There is one confirmed specimen, collected by Eibl-Eibesfeldt at Santa Cruz in 1960 (SMF 5758, photographed). It is frequently reported from visual surveys, but juvenile *Mycteroperca olfax*, abundant at Galapagos, can have spots in a pattern very similar to *E. analogus*. Small *M. olfax* can be distinguished by being longer and slimmer with thin blue edging on the rear dorsal, anal, and caudal fins and the spots on the caudal fin tend to merge into dark lines posteriorly. Humann & DeLoach (2003, p. 87) label a photo of a small *M. olfax* as *E. analogus*, and this guide is reported by author WBS to be used by researchers doing underwater visual surveys and contributing data to databases. Collection records show that almost all specimens are continental, with only rare records from offshore islands. Fourrière et al. (2017, Table S1) list the species at Cocos Island, but the entry stands out for having no museum records and no observations from their extensive field work and only listed as from literature. A recent photograph from a fisherman in Galapagos confirms the species is present, but we list it as a vagrant based on its exceptional rarity.

Calotomus carolinus is changed to a vagrant since almost none are documented in the Galapagos; author WBS recently photographed an adult at North Seymour. McCosker, Taylor & Warner (1978) include *Calotomus carolinus* (as *Calotomus spinidens*) in the new records found on the 1977 California Academy of Sciences' Galapagos Expedition; however, only a single specimen is in museums (CAS 39292). While *C. carolinus* has crossed the East Pacific Barrier and has a resident population in the Revillagigedo Islands and Baja California, *C. spinidens* does not range far into the central Pacific, dropping out after the Marshall Islands in the north and Tonga in the south (Choat & Randall 1986).

Euprepcaranx dorsalis, *Ferdauia orthogrammus*, *Acanthurus triostegus*, and *Xanthichthys mento* are changed to vagrants since they are only sporadically observed and rarely collected, hence not considered a self-sustaining population.

Other notes

Alopias vulpinus (not in lists) has been reported in longline catches off Galapagos (Cerutti-Perreyra et al. 2020), and in the list of Hearn et al. (2014), however no diagnostic photographs are available to discern if it is the coastal *A. vulpinus*, or the similar oceanic and insular *A. pelagicus*.

Myliobatis peruviana is considered the southern TEP sister species of the northern *M. californica*. The *M. longirostris* listed in Mossbrucker et al. (2020) is a misidentified *M. peruviana*.

Facciolella equatorialis (Gilbert, 1891) is considered the senior synonym of *Facciolella gilberti* (Garman, 1899) since both names are used for specimens collected in the same place at different museums, without clear distinguishing features. A single mtDNA lineage, with 3 sequences is documented for the genus from California, 2.16% divergent from *Facciolella "oxyrhynchus"* from the western Pacific.

Narcetes erimelas is listed due to the record MCZ 28476, within the EEZ, of *Bathytroctes alveatus* Garman, 1899, now considered a junior synonym of *N. erimelas* (Fricke, Eschmeyer & Van der Laan 2024).

Lestidiops pacificus (Parr, 1931) is described from a series of specimens from Puerto Vallarta, Mexico and *L. neles* (Harry, 1953) was later described for one different specimen found among the paratypes of *L. pacificus*. Thus far, only *L. pacificus* has been identified in Galapagos (CAS 86744, ID by Hans Ho), but additional

Galapagos juveniles at SIO are recorded as “sp.”.

Ogilbia ventralis (not in lists) was described from Baja California and is recorded from the Galapagos in multiple museum listings. However, Møller, Schwarzhans & Nielsen (2005) reviewed *Ogilbia* and noted that all of the numerous Galapagos *Ogilbia* they examined proved to be *O. deroyi*. Curiously, they could find no specimens of *O. galapagosensis* in museums (the types are lost), but there is a photograph by Tui DeRoy in Grove & Lavenberg (1997, p. 223, fig.113) and this species apparently occurs only in a few shoreline cave systems on Santa Cruz.

Priacanthus (not in lists) has not been recorded in Galapagos (or the TEP south of latitude 18° N), other than a juvenile discussed in Starnes (1988 p. 173: USNM 135644, 41.7 mm SL). The specimen was collected in 1888 by the *Albatross* Expedition in a trawl down to 717 m depth in open ocean about 30 km north of Genovesa. Pelagic *Priacanthus* juveniles at 30–40 mm SL are reported in Starnes (1988), thus this specimen was likely in a pelagic stage and not settled (at over 700 m depth) and has not been included in the list. Starnes (1988) reports the specimen to have scale and gill-raker counts somewhat between the widespread Indo-Pacific *P. hamrur* and the Hawaiian sister species *P. meeki*. He suggested it may be a new TEP species *P. aff. meeki*, but cautioned that no other specimens had been found and added that these fishes are relatively easily collected; if he had known that almost 40 years later there was still no sign of them, he would likely agree it is not a new species. The meristic differences are minor and the variation in the vast range of *P. hamrur* is still not well-documented, thus it cannot be ruled out as a vagrant pelagic juvenile from a central Pacific *P. hamrur* population or a vagrant *P. meeki* from elsewhere.

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References

- Angulo, A., Naranjo-Elizondo, B., Corrales-Ugalde, M. & Cortés, J. (2014) First record of the genus *Paracaristius* (Perciformes: Caristiidae) from the Pacific of Central America, with comments on their association with the siphonophore *Praya reticulata* (Siphonophorae: Prayidae). *Marine Biodiversity Records*, 7, 2014, e132, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755267214001262>
- Aroca, A.K., Tavera, J. & Torres, Y. (2022) Molecular and morphological evaluation of the bonnethead shark complex *Sphyrna tiburo* (Carcharhiniformes: Sphyrnidae). *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 105, 1643–1658. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10641-022-01358-x>
- Béarez, P., Zavalaga, F., Miranda, J., Mennesson, M.I., Campos-León, S. & Jiménez-Prado, P. (2024) *Aulopus chirichignoae*, a new flagfin from the eastern Pacific Ocean (Teleostei, Aulopiformes, Aulopidae). *Zootaxa*, 5458 (1), 108–118. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5458.1.6>
- Bedenbaugh, R. L. (1988) A review of the Pacific members of the gobiid fish genus *Bollmannia* Jordan. Thesis at Old Dominion University, Norfolk, Virginia, USA, 1–56. https://digitalcommons.odu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1328&context=biology_etds
- Betancur-R, R., Wiley, E.O., Arratia, G., Acero, A., Bailly, N., Miya, M., Lecointre, G. & Orti, G. (2017) Phylogenetic classification of bony fishes. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 17, 162. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12862-017-0958-3>
- Bussing, W.A. & López, M.I. (1994) Peces demersales y pelagicos costeros del Pacífico de Centro América Meridional: guía ilustrada/Demersal and pelagic inshore fishes of the Pacific coast of lower Central America: an illustrated guide. Editorial Universidad de Costa Rica, San Jose, Costa Rica, 164 pp.
- Cerutti-Pereyra, F., Moity, N., Dureuil, M., Ramírez-González, J., Reyes, H., Budd, K., Marin Jarrin, J.R. & Salinas-de-León, P. (2020) Artisanal longline fishing the Galapagos Islands –effects on vulnerable megafauna in a UNESCO World Heritage site. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 183, 104995. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2019.104995>
- Choat, J.H. & Randall, J.E. (1986) A revision of the parrotfishes (family Scaridae) of the Great Barrier Reef of Australia with description of a new species. *Records of the Australian Museum*, 38 (4), 175–239. <https://doi.org/10.3853/j.0067-1975.38.1986.181>
- Collette, B.B. & Banford, H.N. (2010) Status of the eastern Pacific agujon needlefish *Tylosurus pacificus* (Steindachner, 1876) (Beloniformes: Belonidae). *Revista de Biología Tropical*, 49 (1) 51–57.
- Dawson, C.E. (1968) Eastern Pacific wormfishes, *Microdesmus dipus* Günther and *Microdesmus dorsipunctatus* sp. nov. *Copeia*, 1968 (3), 512–531.
- Fourrière, M., Alvarado, J.J., Bocos, A.A. & Cortés, J. (2017) Updated checklist and analysis of completeness of the marine fish fauna of Isla del Coco, Pacific of Costa Rica. *Marine Biodiversity*, 47, 813–821. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-016-0501-6>
- Fricke, R., Eschmeyer, W. N. & Van der Laan, R. (Eds.) (2024) *Eschmeyer's catalog of fishes: Genera, Species, and References*. San Francisco (California Academy of Sciences). Electronic version accessed 10 October 2024 at <http://researcharchive.calacademy.org/research/ichthyology/catalog/fishcatmain.asp>
- Grove, J.S. & Lavenberg, R.J. (1997) *The Fishes of the Galápagos Islands*. Stanford University Press, Stanford, CA, USA, 863 pp.
- Grove, J.S., Long, D.J., Robertson, D.R. & Victor, B.C. (2022) List of Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago, Ecuador. *Journal of the Ocean Science Foundation*, 39, 14–22. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7065587>

- Hamilton, H., Saarman, N., Short, G., Sellas, A.B., Moore, B., Hoang, T., Grace, C.L., Gomon, M., Crow, K. & Simison, W.B. (2016) Molecular phylogeny and patterns of diversification in syngnathid fishes. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 107, 388–403.
- Hearn, A., Acuña, D., Ketchum, J.T., Peñaherrera, C., Green, J., Marshall, A. & Shillinger, G. (2014) Elasmobranchs of the Galapagos Marine Reserve. In: Denlinger, J. & Vinuesa, L. (Eds.) *The Galapagos Marine Reserve*. Springer Press, New York, NY, USA, pp. 23–59.
- Herre, A.W.C.T. (1936) Fishes of the Crane Pacific Expedition. *Field Museum of Natural History, Zoological Series*, 21 (1), 1–472.
- Humann, P. & DeLoach, N. (2003) *Reef Fish Identification Galapagos*. New World Publications, Jacksonville, FL, USA & Libri Mundi, Quito, Ecuador, 226 pp.
- Jordan, D.S. & Bollman, C.H. (1890) Descriptions of new species of fishes collected at the Galapagos Islands and along the coast of the United States of Colombia, 1887-'88. Scientific results of explorations by the U. S. Fish Commission steamer Albatross. *Proceedings of the United States National Museum*, 12 (770), 149–183.
- Kotlyar, A.N. (2021) Revision of the genus *Scopelogadus* (Melamphaidae): 3. *S. bispinosus* and *S. perplexus* sp. n. *Journal of Ichthyology*, 61 (1), 1–16.
- Leis, J.M. (2015) Is dispersal of larval reef fishes passive? Chapter 23. In: Mora, C. (Ed.) *Ecology of Fishes on Coral Reefs*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, pp. 223–226.
- Lloris, D., Matallanas, J. & Oliver P. (2005) *Hakes of the world (Family Merlucciidae). An annotated and illustrated catalogue of hake species known to date*. FAO Species Catalogue for Fishery Purposes. No. 2., Rome, Italy, 57 pp.
- Ma, K.Y. & Craig M.T. (2018) An Inconvenient Monophyly: An Update on the Taxonomy of the Groupers (Epinephelidae). *Copeia*, 106 (3), 443–456. <https://doi.org/10.1643/CI-18-055>
- McCosker, J.E. (1998) Book Reviews: The Fishes of the Galápagos Islands. *Copeia*, 1998 (3), 809–812.
- McCosker, J.E. & Long, D.J. (1997) A new species of the deepwater cardinalfish *Epigonus* (Perciformes: Epigonidae) from the Galápagos Islands. *Ichthyological Research*, 44 (2), 125–129.
- McCosker, J.E. & Rosenblatt, R.H. (1984) The Inshore Fish Fauna of the Galápagos Islands. In: Perry, R. (Ed.), *Key Environments: Galapagos*. Pergamon Press, Oxford, UK, pp 133–144.
- McCosker, J.E. & Rosenblatt, R.H. (2010) The fishes of the Galápagos Archipelago: an update. *Proceedings of the California Academy of Sciences*, 61, 167–195.
- McCosker, J.E., Taylor Jr., L.R. & Warner, R.R. (1978) Ichthyological studies at Galapagos. *Noticias de Galápagos*, 27, 13–15.
- McCosker, J.E., Merlen, G., Long, D.J., Gilmore, R.G. & Villon, C. (1997) Deepslope fishes collected during the 1995 eruption of Isla Fernandina, Galápagos. *Noticias de Galápagos*, 58, 22–26.
- Mincarone, M.M., Plachetzki, D., McCord, C.L., Winegard, T.M., Fernholm, B., Gonzalez, C.J., Fudge, D.S. (2021) Review of the hagfishes (Myxinidae) from the Galapagos Islands, with descriptions of four new species and their phylogenetic relationships. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 192, 453–474. <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlaa178>
- Møller, P.R., Schwarzhans, W. & Nielsen, J.G. (2005) Review of the American Dinematchthyini (Teleostei: Bythitidae). Part II. *Ogilbia*. *Aqua, Journal of Ichthyology & Aquatic Biology*, 10 (4), 133–207.
- Morishita, S. & Motomura, H. (2020) *Sphyraena stellata*, a new barracuda from the Indo-Pacific, with redescriptions of *S. helleri* Jenkins, 1901 and *S. novaehollandiae* Günther, 1860 (Perciformes: Sphyraenidae). *Zootaxa*, 2020 May 11;4772(3):zootaxa.4772.3.6. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4772.3.6>.
- Mossbrucker, M.E., Acuña-Marrero, D., Cundy, M.E., Fierro-Arcos, D., Suárez-Moncada, J.M., Rastoin-Laplaine, E. & Salinas-de-León, P. (2023). First records of two rays and three bony fishes for the Galapagos Islands. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 103, e28, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025315423000176>
- Munroe, T.A. & Krabbenhoft, T.J. (2010) Two unusually large pre-transitional tonguefish larvae (Pleuronectiformes: Cynoglossidae: *Symphurus*) collected in oceanic waters near the Galapagos Islands. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 86, 15–33.
- Near, T.J. & Thacker, C.E. (2024) Phylogenetic Classification of Living and Fossil Ray-Finned Fishes (Actino-

- pterygii). *Bulletin of the Peabody Museum of Natural History*, 65 (1), 3–302. <https://doi.org/10.3374/014.065.0101>
- Nelson, J.S., Grande, T.C. & Wilson, M.V.H. (2016) *Fishes of the world. Fifth edition*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ, USA, 707 pp. ISBN 10: 111834233X - ISBN 13: 9781118342336.
- Okamoto, M., Bartsch, P. & Motomura, H. (2012) *Epigonus merleni*, a Junior Synonym of *Epigonus macrops* (Actinopterygii: Perciformes: Epigonidae). *Species Diversity*, 17, 123–126.
- Parin, N.V. (1995) Exocoetidae Peces voladores. In: Fischer, W., Krupp, F., Schneider, W., Sommer, C. & Carpenter, K.E. (Eds.), *Guia FAO para la identificacion de especies para los fines de la pesca: Pacifico centro-oriental. Volumen 1-3*. FAO, Rome, Italy, pp. 1091–1103.
- Parin, N.V. & Borodulina, O.D. (2003) Phylogeny, systematics, and zoogeography of the mesopelagic genus *Astronesthes* (Astronesthidae, Stomiiformes). *Voprosy Ikhtiologii*, 43 (5), 581–601. [In Russian. English translation in *Journal of Ichthyology*, 43 (8), 557–576]
- Parin, N.V., Borodulina, O.D. & Hulley, P.A. (1999) A review of the *Astronestes bouleengeri* species group (Astronesthidae, Stomiiformes), with description of two new species. *Voprosy Ikhtiologii*, 39 (5), 581–594. [In Russian. English translation in *Journal of Ichthyology*, 39 (8), 557–570] [note misspelling of *Astronestes*]
- Parin, N.V., Borodulina, O.D., Konovalenko, I.I. & Kotlyar, A.N. (1990) Oceanic pelagic fishes of the southern East Pacific (composition of fauna and geographic distribution). *Trudy Instituta Oceanologii*, 125, 192–222. [in Russian with English abstract]
- Pérez, M., Fernández-Míguez, M., Matallanas, J., Lloris, D. & Presa, P. (2021) Phylogenetic prospecting for cryptic species of the genus *Merluccius* (Actinopterygii: Merlucciidae). *Scientific Reports*, 11, 5929. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-85008-9>
- Rees, D.J., Poulsen, J.Y., Sutton, T.T., Costa, P.A.S. & Landaeta, M.F. (2020) Global phylogeography suggests extensive eucosmopolitanism in Mesopelagic Fishes (*Maurolicus*: Sternoptychidae). *Scientific Reports*, 2020, Nov 25, 10 (1), 20544. doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-77528-7
- Richards, W.J. & McCosker, J.E. (1998) A new species of the genus *Bellator* (Pisces: Triglidae), with comments on the trigloids of the Galápagos Islands. *Proceedings of the Biological Society of Washington*, 111, 936–941.
- Robertson, D.R., Angulo, A., Baldwin, C.C., Pitassy, D.E., Driskell, A., Weigt, L. & Navarro, I.J.F. (2017) Deep-water bony fishes collected by the B/O Miguel Oliver on the shelf edge of Pacific Central America: an annotated, illustrated and DNA-barcoded checklist. *Zootaxa*, 4348 (1), 1–125. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4348.1.1>
- Robertson, D.R. & Allen, G.R. (2024) *Shorefishes of the Tropical Eastern Pacific: online information system. Version 3.0*, Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, Balboa, Panamá. Electronic version accessed 10 October 2024 at <https://biogeodb.stri.si.edu/sfstep/en/pages>
- Robertson, D.R. & Van Tassell, J. (2023) *Shorefishes of the Greater Caribbean: online information system. Version 3.0* Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute, Balboa, Panamá. Electronic version accessed 10 October 2024 at <https://biogeodb.stri.si.edu/caribbean/en/pages>
- Rosenblatt, R.H. & Walker, B.W. (1963) The marine shore-fishes of the Galápagos Islands. *Occasional Papers of the California Academy of Sciences*, 44, 97–106.
- Salinas-de-León, P., Phillips, B., Ebert, D., Shivji, M., Cerutti-Pereyra, F., Ruck, C., Fisher, C.R. & Marsh, L. (2018) Deep-sea hydrothermal vents as natural egg-case incubators at the Galapagos Rift. *Scientific Reports*, 8, 1788. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-20046-4>
- Salinas-de-León, P., Zanchi, S., Moya-Serrano, A.V., Suarez-Moncada, J. & Hoyos-Padilla, M. (2024) First record of a white shark (*Carcharodon carcharias*) in Ecuadorian waters coinciding with the 2021 La Niña ENSO event. *Environmental Biology of Fishes*, 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10641-024-01620-4>
- Seale, A. (1940) Report on fishes from Allan Hancock Expeditions in the California Academy of Sciences. *Allan Hancock Pacific Expeditions*, 9, 1-46.
- Shakhovskoy, I.B. & Parin, N.V. (2024) A review of the flying fish genus *Cypselurus* (Beloniformes: Exocoetidae). Part 3. Revision of the subgenus *Cypselurus sensu stricto* with descriptions of one new species and four new subspecies and reinstatement of *Cypselurus crockeri* Seale and *Exocoetus socotranus* Steindachner. *Zootaxa*, 5473 (1), 1–125. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5473.1.1>
- Smith, W.L., Ghedotti, M.J., Domínguez-Domínguez, O., McMahan, C.D., Espinoza, E., Martin, R.P., Girard,

- M.G. & Davis, M.P. (2022) Investigations into the ancestry of the Grape-eye Seabass (*Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos*) reveal novel limits and relationships for the Acropomatiformes (Teleostei: Percomorpha). *Neotropical Ichthyology*, 20 (3), e21087598. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1982-0224-2021-0160>
- Starnes, W.C. (1988) Revision, phylogeny and biogeographic comments on the circumtropical marine percoid fish family Priacanthidae. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 43 (2), 117–203.
- Tavera, J.J., Acero P., A., Balart, E.F. & Bernardi, G. (2012) Molecular phylogeny of grunts (Teleostei, Haemulidae), with an emphasis on the ecology, evolution, and speciation history of New World species. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 12, 57. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-12-57>
- Thys, T.M., Whitney, J., Hearn, A., Weng, K.C., Penaherrera, C., Jawad, L., Alfaro-Shigueto, J., Mangel, J.C. & Karl, S.A. (2013) First record of the southern ocean sunfish, *Mola ramsayi*, in the Galápagos Marine Reserve. *Marine Biodiversity Records*, 6, 2013, e70. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755267213000377>
- Todd, V.L.G. & Grove, J.S. (2010) First records of golden trevally (*Gnathodon speciosus*, Carangidae), sharp-tail mola (*Masturus lanceolatus*, Molidae) and evidence for white shark (*Carcharodon carcharias*, Lamnidae) in the Galapagos Islands, Ecuador. *Marine Biodiversity Records*, 3, 2010, e104. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1755267210000771>
- Torii, A., Harold, A.S. & Ozawa, T. (2003) Redescription of type specimens of three *Bregmaceros* species (Gadiformes: Bregmacerotidae): *B. bathyamster*, *B. rarisquamosus*, and *B. cayorum*. *Memoirs of the Faculty of Fisheries, Kagoshima University*, 52, 23–32. [note *bathyamster* misspelling in original]
- Valencia-Mendez, O., Catania, D. & López-Pérez, A. (2018) The Red-fin Goby, *Evorthodus minutus* Meek & Hildebrand, 1928: a new record from Santa Cruz Island, Galapagos Archipelago. *Check List*, 15 (1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.15560/15.1.1>
- Victor, B.C. (in press) Rapid long-distance multispecies transport of shorefish larvae to the oceanic tropical eastern Pacific, revealed by DNA barcodes and otolith aging of larvae captured over the Galapagos Rift. *Fishery Bulletin*, Moser Symposium, in press.
- Victor, B.C., Wellington, G.M., Robertson, D.R. & Ruttenberg, B.I. (2001) The effect of the El Niño-southern oscillation event on the distribution of reef-associated labrid fishes in the eastern Pacific Ocean. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 69 (1), 279–288.

TABLE 1 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
(683 spp. in taxonomic order)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	Branchiostomatidae	R	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Centrophoridae	R
<i>Eptatretus goslnei</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	Echinorhinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	Torpedinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Rhinobatidae	R
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	Rajidae	RE
<i>Myxine greggi</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	Rajidae	R
<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Myxine martinii</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	Gurgesiellidae	R
<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	Heterodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Rhincodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus longus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	Odontaspidae	R	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	Potamotrygonidae	R
<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	Lamnidae	V	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	Aetobatidae	R
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Lamnidae	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	Myliobatidae	V
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	Myliobatidae	R
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Rhinopteridae	R
<i>Apristurus kampaie</i>	Pentanchidae	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	RE	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus albigipinnis</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Carcharhinidae	V	<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Elops affinis</i>	Elopidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Albula esuncula</i>	Albulidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	Halosauridae	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	Notacanthidae	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ilyophis arx</i>	Synphobranchidae	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	Synphobranchidae	R
<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Galeocerdonidae	R	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	Myrocongridae	R
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	Dalatiidae	R	<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	Etmopteridae	R	<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	Muraenidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	Nemichthyidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	Serrivomeridae	R
<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	Anguillidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	Engraulidae	V
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	Clupeidae	RE
<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	Dussumieriidae	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	Alosidae	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Bathytroctes microlepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Narcetes erimelas</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	Chlopsidae	R	<i>Platyroctes apus</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	Chanidae	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Argentina alicee</i>	Argentinidae	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Leuroglossus stilbeus</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	Opisthoproctidae	R
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	Ophichthidae	V	<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	Nettastomatidae	R	<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Heteroconger klausewitzii</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Maurolucus australis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	Sternoptychidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Diaphus rafenesqii</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Diaphus theta</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Yarella argentiola</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Hygophum reinhardti</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Loweina rara</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Idiacanthus antrostomus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Myctophum affine</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	Ateleopodidae	R	<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	Aulopidae	R	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	Chlorophthalmidae	R	<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Triphoturus oculeum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Zu cristatus</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	Notosudidae	R	<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	Regalacidae	R
<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	Stylephoridae	R
<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	Bregmacerotidae	V
<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	Trachyrincidae	R
<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	Paralepididae	R	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Stemonosudis macrura</i>	Paralepididae	R	<i>Gadella filifer</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	Evermannellidae	R	<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	Moridae	RE
<i>Scopelengys tristis</i>	Neoscopelidae	R	<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	Macrouridae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Bellottia</i> sp.	Bythitidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Cataetix rubirostris</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Cataetix simus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE
<i>Melamphaeus laeviceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE
<i>Melamphaeus spinifer</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Seriolella violacea</i>	Centrolophidae	R
<i>Poromitra crassiceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Psenes sio</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Tetragonurus atlanticus</i>	Tetragonuridae	R
<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Peprilus medius</i>	Stromateidae	R
<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	Rondeletiidae	R	<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R
<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	Cetomimidae	R	<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R
<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	Trachichthyidae	RE	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	Anoplogastridae	R	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Holocentridae	R	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	Holocentridae	R	<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	Holocentridae	R	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Carapus mourlani</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Paracaristius</i> sp.	Caristiidae	R
<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	Bramidae	R
<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	Bramidae	R
<i>Lepophidium pardale</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Gempylidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	Cyclopsettidae	V
<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	Cyclopsettidae	V
<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Bothus mancus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	Bothidae	V
<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	Achiridae	V
<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	Callionymidae	R	<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	Soleidae	R
<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Aulostomidae	R	<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R
<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae	R	<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R
<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Fistulariidae	V	<i>Symphurus varius</i>	Cynoglossidae	R
<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Xiphiidae	R
<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Apogon dovii</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Caranx caballus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Eleotris picta</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Caranx caninus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Carangidae	V
<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Eleotris cableae</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Evorthodus minutus</i>	Gobiidae	V	<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Euprepocaranx dorsalis</i>	Carangidae	V
<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	Gobiidae	V	<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	Carangidae	V
<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	Carangidae	V
<i>Tigrigobius nesiotis</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	Centropomidae	R	<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae	V	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	Sphyraenidae	R	<i>Selene peruviana</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	Sphyraenidae	R	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Polydactylus approximans</i>	Polynemidae	V	<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	Cyclopsettidae	RE	<i>Seriola rivirolana</i>	Carangidae	R
<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	Cyclopsettidae	R	<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	Carangidae	V

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon spilonopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Phtheichthys lineatus</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora albescens</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora osteochir</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora remora</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	Mugilidae	R
<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Coryphaenidae	R	<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	Mugilidae	R
<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Coryphaenidae	R	<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	Mugilidae	RE
<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	Opistognathidae	RE	<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	Mugilidae	RE
<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	Gobiesocidae	R
<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Tomicodon chilensis</i>	Gobiesocidae	R
<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Tomicodon petersii</i>	Gobiesocidae	R
<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	Pomacentridae	RE	<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	Tripterygiidae	RE
<i>Azurina intercerusma</i>	Pomacentridae	V	<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	Labrisomidae	RE
<i>Chromis alta</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	Labrisomidae	R
<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	Labrisomidae	R
<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	Labrisomidae	RE
<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	Labrisomidae	R
<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	Labrisomidae	R
<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	Labrisomidae	RE
<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	Labrisomidae	RE
<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE
<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	Atherinopsidae	R	<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE
<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	Atherinopsidae	R	<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE
<i>Cololabis adocetus</i>	Scomberesocidae	R	<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R
<i>Ablennes hians</i>	Belonidae	R	<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE
<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	Belonidae	R	<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE
<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	Belonidae	R	<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	Belonidae	V	<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	Belonidae	V	<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	Blenniidae	V
<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	Hemiramphidae	V	<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	Malakichthyidae	R
<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	Priacanthidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	Malacanthidae	R	<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	Epinephelidae	V
<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	Lutjanidae	V	<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	Grammistidae	R
<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Grammistidae	R
<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Lutjanidae	V	<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	Grammistidae	R
<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	Liopropomatidae	R
<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	Liopropomatidae	R
<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	Serranidae	V
<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Serranidae	RE
<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	Serranidae	RE
<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Anthias noeli</i>	Anthiidae	R
<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	Anthiidae	V
<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	Anthiidae	R
<i>Microlepidotus lethoprists</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Orthopristis cantherina</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	V
<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	Haemulidae	V	<i>Decodon melasma</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	Labridae	V
<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	Haemulidae	V	<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	Sparidae	RE	<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	Sparidae	R	<i>Halichoeres melanotis</i>	Labridae	V
<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	Sparidae	RE	<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Corvula macrops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	Sciaenidae	V	<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Pareques perissa</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	Labridae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Scarus compressus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Scarus perrico</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Girella freminivillii</i>	Girellidae	RE
<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Cirrhichthys oxycephalus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Cirrhitis rivulatus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	Epigonidae	R
<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Howella pammelas</i>	Howellidae	R
<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	Zoarcidae	R	<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	Lobotidae	V
<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	Zoarcidae	R	<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	Pomacanthidae	R
<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	Zoarcidae	R	<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	Pomacanthidae	V
<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	Ammodytidae	R	<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	Uranoscopidae	V	<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Bellator farrago</i>	Triglidae	R	<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	Triglidae	R	<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Prionotus miles</i>	Triglidae	RE	<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Prionotus stephanophrys</i>	Triglidae	R	<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE	<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE	<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	Luvaridae	R
<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae	R
<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	Acanthuridae	V
<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Acanthuridae	R
<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Acanthuridae	V
<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae	R
<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE	<i>Naso annulatus</i>	Acanthuridae	V
<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	Acanthuridae	V
<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	Acanthuridae	V
<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	Acanthuridae	V
<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	Scorpaenidae	V	<i>Prionurus laticlavus</i>	Acanthuridae	R
<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	Lophiidae	R
<i>Psychrolutes sio</i>	Psychrolutidae	R	<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE
<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R
<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	Kuhliidae	R	<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R
<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	Oplegnathidae	R	<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE
<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Kyphosidae	V	<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R
<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	Antennariidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	Antennariidae	V	<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	Chaunacidae	R			
<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	Melanocetidae	R			
<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	Oneirodidae	R			
<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	Oneirodidae	R			
<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	Oneirodidae	R			
<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	Oneirodidae	R			
<i>Cryptopsaras coueseii</i>	Ceratiidae	R			
<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	Gigantactinidae	R			
<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	Linophrynidae	R			
<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	Molidae	R			
<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	Molidae	R			
<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	Diodontidae	R			
<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	Diodontidae	V			
<i>Diodon eydouxii</i>	Diodontidae	R			
<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>	Diodontidae	R			
<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Diodontidae	R			
<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	Ostraciidae	V			
<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	Ostraciidae	R			
<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	Monacanthidae	V			
<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae	R			
<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	Monacanthidae	V			
<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Balistidae	R			
<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Balistidae	R			
<i>Melichthys niger</i>	Balistidae	R			
<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	Balistidae	V			
<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	Balistidae	R			

TABLE 2 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
(683 spp. in family alphabetical order)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	Aulopidae	R
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Aulostomidae	R
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Melichthys niger</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Prionurus laticlavius</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	Achiridae	V	<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	Aetobatidae	R	<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Albula esuncula</i>	Albulidae	V	<i>Leuroglossus stilbeus</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Bathytroctes microlepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Ablennes hians</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Narctes erimelas</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	Belonidae	V
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	Belonidae	V
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	Alosidae	R	<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	Ammodytidae	R	<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	Anguillidae	R	<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	Anoplogastridae	R	<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	Blenniidae	V
<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	Antennariidae	V	<i>Bothus mancus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	Bothidae	V
<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	Bramidae	R
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	Bramidae	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	Anthiidae	V	<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	Branchiostomatidae	R
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	Bregmacerotidae	V
<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Bellottia</i> sp.	Bythitidae	R
<i>Apogon dovii</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Cataetx rubirostris</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Argentina aliceeae</i>	Argentinidae	R	<i>Cataetx simus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	Ateleopodidae	R	<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	Atherinopsidae	R	<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	Callionymidae	R
<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	Atherinopsidae	R	<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	Carangidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Caranx caballus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cryptopsaras coueseii</i>	Ceratiidae	R
<i>Caranx caninus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	Cetomimidae	R
<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE
<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Eupreopcaranx dorsalis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	Chanidae	R
<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	Chaunacidae	R
<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R
<i>Selene peruviana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R
<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Seriola rivirolana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Hydrolagus n. sp.</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	Chlopsidae	R
<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	Chlorophthalmidae	R
<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cirrhitus rivulatus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Carcharhinidae	V	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	Clupeidae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Heteroconger klausewitzi</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Paraconger similis</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Paracaristius sp.</i>	Caristiidae	R	<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Seriolella violacea</i>	Centrolophidae	R	<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Centrophoridae	R	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	Centropomidae	R	<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	Cyclopsettidae	RE

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	Cyclosettidae	R	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	Cyclosettidae	V	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	Cyclosettidae	V	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	Epinephelidae	V
<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	Etmopteridae	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	Dalatiidae	R	<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	Evermannellidae	R
<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Hypanus longus</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon spilonopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	Diodontidae	V	<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Diodon eydouxii</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae	R
<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	Dussumieriidae	R	<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Fistulariidae	V
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Galeocerdonidae	R
<i>Phtheichthys lineatus</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Remora albescens</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Remora osteochir</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Remora remora</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	Echinorhinidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Eleotris picta</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Elops affinis</i>	Elopidae	V	<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	Engraulidae	R	<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	Gigantactinidae	R
<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	Engraulidae	R	<i>Girella freminivillii</i>	Girellidae	RE
<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	Engraulidae	V	<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	Gobiesocidae	R
<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	Engraulidae	R	<i>Tomicodon chilensis</i>	Gobiesocidae	R
<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	Epigonidae	R	<i>Tomicodon petersii</i>	Gobiesocidae	R
<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Epinephelidae	R	<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	Heterodontidae	R
<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Hexanchidae	R
<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	Hexanchidae	R
<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Evorthodus minutus</i>	Gobiidae	V	<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Howella pammelas</i>	Howellidae	R
<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	Gobiidae	V	<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	Ipnopidae	R
<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	Ipnopidae	R
<i>Tigri gobioides</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	Ipnopidae	R
<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	Kuhliidae	R
<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Kyphosidae	V
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	Gurgesiellidae	R	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	V
<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Decodon melasma</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	Labridae	V
<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Orthopristis cantherina</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Halichoeres melanotis</i>	Labridae	V
<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	Haemulidae	V	<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	Haemulidae	V	<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	Halosauridae	R	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Scarus compressus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	Hemiramphidae	V	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Scarus perrico</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	Hemiramphidae	R	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	Malacanthidae	R
<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	Malakichthyidae	R
<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Melamphaeus laeviceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Melamphaeus spinifer</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	Lamnidae	V	<i>Poromitra crassiceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Lamnidae	R	<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	Linophrynidae	R	<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	Liopropomatidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	Liopropomatidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	Melanocetidae	R
<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	Lobotidae	V	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	Lophiidae	R	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	Lutjanidae	V	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	Monacanthidae	V
<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae	R
<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	Monacanthidae	V
<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Lutjanidae	V	<i>Gadella filifer</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	Luvaridae	R	<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	Moridae	RE
<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	Mugilidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	Mugilidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	Mugilidae	RE

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Loweina rara</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myctophum affine</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myctophum aurolaterdatum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Triphoturus oculeum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	Myliobatidae	V
<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	Myliobatidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	Myrocongridae	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Eptatretus mccooskeri</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myxine greggi</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myxine martinii</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	Myxinidae	RE
<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	Nemichthyidae	R
<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopelengys tristis</i>	Neoscopelidae	R
<i>Diaphus rafenesqii</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	Nettastomatidae	R
<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Diaphus theta</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Hygophum reinhardti</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Psenes sio</i>	Nomeidae	R
<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	Notacanthidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	Notosudidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	Odontaspidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Stemonosudis macrura</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Haliieutopsis tumifrons</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Apristurus kampa</i>	Pentanchidae	R
<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	RE
<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Yarella argentiola</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Platyroctes apus</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Polydactylus approximans</i>	Polynemidae	V
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	Pomacanthidae	R
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	Pomacanthidae	V
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	Pomacentridae	RE
<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	Pomacentridae	V
<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	Ophichthidae	V	<i>Chromis alta</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Carapus mourlani</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	Potamotrygonidae	R
<i>Lepophidium pardale</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Psychrolutes sio</i>	Psychrolutidae	R
<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	Rajidae	RE
<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	Ophidiidae	R	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	Rajidae	R
<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	Opisthoproctidae	R	<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	Regalacidae	R
<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	Opistognathidae	RE	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Rhincodontidae	R
<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	Oplegnathidae	R	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Rhinobatidae	R
<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	Ostraciidae	V	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Rhinopteridae	R
<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	Ostraciidae	R	<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	Rondeletiidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Corvula macrops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	Sciaenidae	V	<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	Serranidae	RE
<i>Pareques perissa</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	Serrivomeridae	R
<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	Soleidae	R
<i>Cololabis adocetus</i>	Scomberesocidae	R	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	Sparidae	R
<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae	V
<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Sphyrnidae	R
<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Sphyrnidae	R
<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Maurollicus australis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE	<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE	<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE	<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	Scorpaenidae	V	<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Idiacanthus anrostomus</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Peprilus medius</i>	Stromateidae	R
<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	Stylephoridae	R
<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Ilyophip arx</i>	Synphobranchidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	Synphobranchidae	R	<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	Syngnathidae	R			
<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Syngnathidae	R			
<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	Synodontidae	R			
<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	Synodontidae	R			
<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	Synodontidae	R			
<i>Tetragonurus atlanticus</i>	Tetragonuridae	R			
<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	Tetraodontidae	V			
<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R			
<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	Torpedinidae	R			
<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	Trachichthyidae	RE			
<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	Trachipteridae	R			
<i>Zu cristatus</i>	Trachipteridae	R			
<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	Trachyrincidae	R			
<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	Triakidae	R			
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	Triakidae	R			
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	Triakidae	R			
<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	Trichiuridae	R			
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	Trichiuridae	R			
<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	Trichiuridae	R			
<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	Trichiuridae	R			
<i>Bellator farrago</i>	Triglidae	R			
<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	Triglidae	R			
<i>Prionotus miles</i>	Triglidae	RE			
<i>Prionotus stephanophrys</i>	Triglidae	R			
<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	Tripterygiidae	RE			
<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	Uranoscopidae	V			
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Xiphiidae	R			
<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae	R			

TABLE 3

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
endemic species (67 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Myxine greggi</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Myxine martinii</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Dibranchus cracens</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Dibranchus discors</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE
<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	CLUPEIDAE	RE	<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE
<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	CYCLOPSETTA	RE	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	OPISTOGNATHIDAE	RE
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE	<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	PENTANCHIDAE	RE
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	RE
<i>Platygilhellus rubellulus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	RAJIDAE	RE
<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE	<i>Pareques perissa</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE	<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Girella freminvillii</i>	GIRELLIDAE	RE	<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE
<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE
<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE
<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	SPARIDAE	RE
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	SPARIDAE	RE
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	TRACHICHTHYIDAE	RE
<i>Malaccoctenus zonogaster</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Prionotus miles</i>	TRIGLIDAE	RE
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	TRIPTERYGIIDAE	RE
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE			
<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE			
<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	MORIDAE	RE			
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE			
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			

TABLE 4

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish vagrants (65 spp.) & other vagrants (12 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	LUTJANIDAE	V
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	V
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	MONACANTHIDAE	V
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	MONACANTHIDAE	V
<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	ACHIRIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Albula esuncula</i>	ALBULIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	BALISTIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	BALISTIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	BALISTIDAE	V	<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	BELONIDAE	V	<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	V
<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	BELONIDAE	V	<i>Polydactylus approximans</i>	POLYNEMIDAE	V
<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	BLENNIIDAE	V	<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	POMACANTHIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	SCIAENIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	SERRANIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Sphyræna barracuda</i>	SPHYRAENIDAE	V
<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	V	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	V	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Cyclichthys spilostylus</i>	DIODONTIDAE	V	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	ELEOTRIDAE	V	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Eleotris picta</i>	ELEOTRIDAE	V	<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	URANOSCOPIDAE	V
<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	ELEOTRIDAE	V			
<i>Elops affinis</i>	ELOPIDAE	V	NON-SHALLOW-SHOREFISH CATEGORY VAGRANTS (12)		
<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	V	<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	V
<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	V	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	BOTHIDAE	V
<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	FISTULARIIDAE	V	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	BREGMACEROTIDAE	V
<i>Evorthodus minutus</i>	GOBIIDAE	V	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	GOBIIDAE	V	<i>Eupreopocaranx dorsalis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	HAEMULIDAE	V	<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	HAEMULIDAE	V	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	V	<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	V	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	V
<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	V	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	LAMNIDAE	V
<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	LABRIDAE	V	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	MYLIOBATIDAE	V
<i>Halichoeres melanotis</i>	LABRIDAE	V	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	OSTRACIIDAE	V
<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	LOBOTIDAE	V			

TABLE 5 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish residents (261 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	CHANIDAE	R
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>	CIRRHITIDAE	R
<i>Prionurus laticlavius</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Cirrhitus rivulatus</i>	CIRRHITIDAE	R
<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	ALOSIDAE	R	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	CIRRHITIDAE	R
<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	AMMODYTIDAE	R	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	CLUPEIDAE	R
<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	ANGUILLIDAE	R	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	CLUPEIDAE	R
<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	R	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	CLUPEIDAE	RE
<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	R	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	CLUPEIDAE	R
<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	R	<i>Heteroconger klausewitzi</i>	CONGRIDAE	R
<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	APOGONIDAE	R	<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	RE
<i>Apogon dovii</i>	APOGONIDAE	R	<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	R
<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	APOGONIDAE	R	<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	CYNOGLOSSIDAE	R
<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	ATHERINOPSIDAE	R	<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIIDAE	RE
<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	ATHERINOPSIDAE	R	<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIIDAE	R
<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	AULOSTOMIDAE	R	<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIIDAE	RE
<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIIDAE	RE
<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	DASYATIDAE	R
<i>Melichthys niger</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Hypanus longus</i>	DASYATIDAE	R
<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE
<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE
<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R
<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R
<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R
<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	DUSSUMIERIIDAE	R
<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	R
<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	R
<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	BOTHIDAE	R	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	R
<i>Bothus mancus</i>	BOTHIDAE	R	<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	BRANCHIOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	CALLIONYMIDAE	R	<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	CENTROPOMIDAE	R	<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	FISTULARIIDAE	R
<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R	<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	GERREIDAE	R
<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R	<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	GERREIDAE	R
<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R	<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	GERREIDAE	R
<i>Prognathodes carlhubbisi</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R	<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	GERREIDAE	R

TABLE 5 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish residents (261 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Girella freminivillii</i>	GIRELLIDAE	RE	<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	GOBIESOCIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Tomocodon chilensis</i>	GOBIESOCIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Tomocodon petersii</i>	GOBIESOCIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Scarus compressus</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Scarus perrico</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	GRAMMISTIDAE	R	<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	GRAMMISTIDAE	R	<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	GRAMMISTIDAE	R	<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Orthopristis cantharina</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	LATILIDAE	R
<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	LATILIDAE	R
<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R	<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	LIOPROPOMATIDAE	R
<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R	<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	HETERODONTIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	HOLOCENTRIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	HOLOCENTRIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	HOLOCENTRIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	KUHLIIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	MALACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R	<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	MALAKICHTHYIDAE	R

TABLE 5 (p. 3)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish residents (261 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	MONACANTHIDAE	R	<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	MUGILIDAE	R	<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	MUGILIDAE	R	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	OPISTOGNATHIDAE	RE
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE	<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	OPLEGNATHIDAE	R
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	OSTRACIIDAE	R
<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	MULLIDAE	R	<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	PARALICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	MULLIDAE	R	<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	PARALICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	POMACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	RE
<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Chromis alta</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	POTAMOTRYGONIDAE	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	PRIACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	PRIACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	OGCOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	RAJIDAE	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	RHINOBATIDAE	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Corvula macrops</i>	SCIAENIDAE	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE	<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	SCIAENIDAE	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Pareques perissa</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE	<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	SERRANIDAE	R
<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	SERRANIDAE	R
<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R	<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE
<i>Carapus mourlani</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R	<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	SERRANIDAE	R
<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R	<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	SOLEIDAE	R
<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	SPARIDAE	RE
<i>Lepophidium pardale</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R	<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	SPARIDAE	R

TABLE 5 (p. 4)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

shallow shorefish residents (261 spp.)

nearshore pelagics (28 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	SPARIDAE	RE	<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	SPHYRAENIDAE	R	<i>Caranx caballus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	SPHYRAENIDAE	R	<i>Caranx caninus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	SYNODONTIDAE	R	<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	SYNODONTIDAE	R	<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	SYNODONTIDAE	R	<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Eupreopcaranx dorsalis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	TORPEDINIDAE	R	<i>Selene peruviana</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Prionotus miles</i>	TRIGLIDAE	RE	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Prionotus stephanophrys</i>	TRIGLIDAE	R	<i>Seriola peruana</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	TRIPTERYGIIDAE	RE	<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	ZANCLIDAE	R	<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
			<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
			<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
			<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
			<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
			<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
			<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	CORYPHAENIDAE	R
			<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	CORYPHAENIDAE	R

TABLE 6 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
deepwater non-pelagic (121 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	R	<i>Howella pammelas</i>	HOWELLIDAE	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	V	<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	IPNOPIDAE	R
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	R	<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	IPNOPIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	IPNOPIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Decodon melasma</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	LIOPROPOMATIDAE	R
<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	AULOPIDAE	R	<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE
<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	BOTHIDAE	V	<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE
<i>Bellottia</i> sp.	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	LOPHIIDAE	R
<i>Cataetyx rubirostris</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Cataetyx simus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	CENTROPHORIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	CHAUNACIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	R	<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	CHLOPSIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	CHLOROPHTHALMIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Gadella filifer</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	MORIDAE	RE
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	CYNOGLOSSIDAE	R	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	MYROCONGRIDAE	R
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	CYNOGLOSSIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	DASYATIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	ECHINORHINIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	EPIGONIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R	<i>Myxine martinii</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	ETMOPTERIDAE	R	<i>Myxine greggi</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	GURGESIELLIDAE	R	<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	HALOSAURIDAE	R	<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	HEXANCHIDAE	R	<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	NETTASTOMATIDAE	R
<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	HEXANCHIDAE	R	<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	NOTACANTHIDAE	R

TABLE 6 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
deepwater non-pelagic (121 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	ZOARCIDAE	R
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE			
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	R			
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	R			
<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE			
<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Apristurus kampae</i>	PENTANCHIDAE	R			
<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	PENTANCHIDAE	RE			
<i>Psychrolutes sio</i>	PSYCHROLUTIDAE	R			
<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	RAJIDAE	RE			
<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE			
<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE			
<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE			
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE			
<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	SERRANIDAE	R			
<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE			
<i>Ilyophis arx</i>	SYNAPHOBRANCHIDAE	R			
<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	SYNAPHOBRANCHIDAE	R			
<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	TRACHICHTHYIDAE	RE			
<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	TRACHYRINCIDAE	R			
<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	TRIAKIDAE	R			
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	TRIAKIDAE	R			
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	TRIAKIDAE	R			
<i>Bellator farrago</i>	TRIGLIDAE	R			
<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	TRIGLIDAE	R			
<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	ZOARCIDAE	R			
<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	ZOARCIDAE	R			

TABLE 7 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
offshore pelagics (96 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	AETOBATIDAE	R	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	ALOPIIDAE	R	<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Ablennes hians</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	BRAMIDAE	R	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R
<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	BRAMIDAE	R	<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R
<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	BREGMACEROTIDAE	V	<i>Istiompax indica</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	CARANGIDAE	R	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Kajikia audax</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	V	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	LAMNIDAE	V
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	LAMNIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	LUVARIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Paracaristius</i> sp.	CARISTIIDAE	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Seriolaella violacea</i>	CENTROLOPHIDAE	R	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	MOLIDAE	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	DALATIIDAE	R	<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	MOLIDAE	R
<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	DASYATIDAE	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	MYLIOBATIDAE	V
<i>Diodon eydouxi</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R	<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	MYLIOBATIDAE	R
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Phtheichthys lineatus</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora albescens</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora osteochir</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora remora</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Psenes sio</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	ODONTASPIDIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	OSTRACIIDAE	V
<i>Cheilopogon spilonotopterus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	REGALECIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	RHINCODONTIDAE	R
<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	RHINOPTERIDAE	R
<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Cololabis adoceta</i>	SCOMBERESOCIDAE	R
<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Auxis rochei</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Auxis thazard</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	GALEOCERDONIDAE	R	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R	<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R

TABLE 7 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
offshore pelagics (96 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R			
<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R			
<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R			
<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R			
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	SPHYRNIDAE	R			
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	SPHYRNIDAE	R			
<i>Peprilus medius</i>	STROMATEIDAE	R			
<i>Tetragonurus atlanticus</i>	TETRAGONURIDAE	R			
<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R			
<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	TRACHIPTERIDAE	R			
<i>Zu cristatus</i>	TRACHIPTERIDAE	R			
<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R			
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R			
<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R			
<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R			
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	XIPHIIDAE	R			

TABLE 8 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
mesopelagics (112 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Bathytroctes macrolepis</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus theta</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Narcetes erimelas</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	ALOPTIIDAE	R	<i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	ANOPLOGASTRIDAE	R	<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Argentina alicae</i>	ARGENTINIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	ATELEPODIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	BATHYLAGIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Leuroglossus stilbius</i>	BATHYLAGIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cryptosaras coueseii</i>	CERATIIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	CETOMIMIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	CHIASMODONTIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	CHIASMODONTIDAE	R	<i>Loweina rara</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	EVERMANNELLIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	GIGANTACTINIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum affine</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	LINOPHRYNIDAE	R	<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Melamphaes laeviceps</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Triphoturus oculeum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Melamphaes spinifer</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	NEMICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra crassiceps</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Scopelengys tristis</i>	NEOSCOPELIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	NOTOSUDIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R
<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R
<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	OPISTHOPROCTIDAE	R
<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	PARALEPIDIDAE	R
<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	MELANOCETIDAE	R	<i>Stemonosudis macrura</i>	PARALEPIDIDAE	R
<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R	<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R	<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Diaphus rafinesqii</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R	<i>Yarrella argenteola</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R

TABLE 8 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
mesopelagics (112 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R			
<i>Platytroctes apus</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R			
<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	RONDELETIIDAE	R			
<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	SCOPELARCHIDAE	R			
<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	SCOPELARCHIDAE	R			
<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	SCOPELARCHIDAE	R			
<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	SERRIVOMERIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Mauroliticus australis</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Idiacanthus antrostomus</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	STYLEPHORIDAE	R			

TABLE 9 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

following Grove et al. (2022); in taxonomic order (with changes in **bold**)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	Branchiostomatidae	R	<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	Echinorhinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	Torpedinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Rhinobatidae	R
<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	Rajidae	RE
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	Rajidae	R
<i>Myxine greggi</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Myxine martinii</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	Gurgesiellidae	R
<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	Heterodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus longus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Rhincodontidae	R	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	Odontaspidae	R	<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	Potamotrygonidae	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	Aetobatidae	R
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Lamnidae	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	Myliobatidae	V
<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	Lamnidae	V	<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	Myliobatidae	R
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Rhinopteridae	R
<i>Apristurus kampae</i>	Pentanchidae	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	RE	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Chimaera</i> sp.	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Carcharhinidae	V	<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Elops affinis</i>	Elopidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Albula esuncula</i>	Albulidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	Halosauridae	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	Notacanthidae	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ilyophis arx</i>	Synphobranchidae	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	Synphobranchidae	R
<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Galeocerdonidae	R	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	Myrocongridae	R
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna mokarran</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna tiburo</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	Dalatiidae	R	<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	Etmopteridae	R	<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Centrophoridae	R	<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	Muraenidae	R
			<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	Muraenidae	V
			<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Muraenidae	R

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	Engraulidae	V
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	Clupeidae	RE
<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	Dussumieriidae	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	Alosidae	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Bathytroctes macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Narcetes erimelas</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	Chlopsidae	R	<i>Platyroctes apus</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Aptерichthys equatorialis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	Chanidae	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Argentina alicae</i>	Argentinidae	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenyis</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Leuroglossus stilbius</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	Opisthoproctidae	R
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Paraletarchus opercularis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	Ophichthidae	V	<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	Nettastomatidae	R	<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	Congridae	V	<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Bathycongrus n. sp.</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Chiloconger dentatus</i>	Congridae	V	<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Gnathophis cinctus</i>	Congridae	V	<i>Mauroliticus australis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Heteroconger klausewitzii</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Japonoconger n. sp.</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	Nemichthyidae	R	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	Serrivomeridae	R	<i>Yarella argentiola</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	Anguillidae	R	<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	Stomiidae	R
<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	Engraulidae	R	<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Astronesthes martensii</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Idiacanthus antrostomus</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	Stomiidae	R
			<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	Stomiidae	R

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 3)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Stomias boa</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Triphoturus ocaleum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	Ateleopodidae	R	<i>Zu cristatus</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	Aulopidae	R	<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	Regalacidae	R
<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	Chlorophthalmidae	R	<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	Stylephoridae	R
<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	Bregmacerotidae	V
<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros macclellandi</i>	Bregmacerotidae	R
<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Merluccius gayi</i>	Merlucciidae	R
<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	Trachyrincidae	R
<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	Scopelarchidae	R	<i>Gadella filifer</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	Notosudidae	R	<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	Moridae	R
<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	Synodontidae	R	<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	Paralepididae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	Evermannellidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Scopelengys tristis</i>	Neoscopelidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus rafenesqii</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diaphus theta</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Melamphaeus laeviceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Melamphaeus spinifer</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra crassiceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Loweina rara</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Myctophum affine</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	Rondeletiidae	R
<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	Cetomimidae	R
<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	Trachichthyidae	R
<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	Anoplogasteridae	R
<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Cataetys sp. vs simus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Lepophidium pardale</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	Ophidiidae	R
			<i>Carapus mourlani</i>	Ophidiidae	R

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 4)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	Ophiidae	R	<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	Ophiidae	R	<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	Trichiuridae	R
Bellottia sp.	Bythitidae	R	<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	Mullidae	R
<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	Bythitidae	RE	<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	Mullidae	R
Cataetx rubirostris	Bythitidae	R	<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	Callionymidae	R
Cataetx simus	Bythitidae	R	<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Aulostomidae	R
<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae	R
<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Fistulariidae	V
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	Apogonidae	R
Porichthys margaritatus	Batrachoididae	R	<i>Apogon dovii</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Seriolella violacea</i>	Centrolophidae	R	<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Eleotris picta</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	Nomeidae	R	Bolmannia macropoma	Gobiidae	R
<i>Psenes sio</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	Gobiidae	RE
Tetragonurus atlanticus	Tetragonuridae	R	<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Peprilus medius</i>	Stromateidae	R	<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R	<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R	Evorthodus minutus	Gobiidae	V
<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	Gobiidae	V
<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	Centropomidae	R
<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae	V
Thunnus alalunga	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Scombridae	R	Polydactylus approximans	Polynemidae	V
Paracaristius sp.	Caristiidae	R	<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	Cyclosettidae	RE
<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	Bramidae	R	<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	Cyclosettidae	R
<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	Bramidae	R	<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	Cyclosettidae	V
<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	Cyclosettidae	V
<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Bothus mancus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	Bothidae	V
<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	Trichiuridae	R			
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	Trichiuridae	R			

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 5)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R	<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R	<i>Phtheichthys lineatus</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	Achiridae	V	<i>Remora albescens</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	Soleidae	R	<i>Remora australis</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Remora osteochir</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Remora remora</i>	Echeneidae	R
<i>Nematistius pectoralis</i>	Nematistiidae	V	<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Xiphiidae	R	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	Opistognathidae	R
<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	Pomacentridae	RE
<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	Pomacentridae	V
<i>Caranx caballus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chromis alta</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx caninus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	Atherinopsidae	R
<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	Atherinopsidae	R
<i>Eupreopocaranx dorsalis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Cololabis adocetus</i>	Scomberesocidae	R
<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Ablennes hians</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	Belonidae	V
<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	Belonidae	V
<i>Selene peruviana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	Hemiramphidae	V
<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon spilonotopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	Carangidae	R			

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 6)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Cypselurus angusticeps</i>	Exocoetidae	✓	<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	Priacanthidae	R
<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	Malacanthidae	R
<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	Latilidae	R
<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	Latilidae	R
<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Hirundichthys rondeletii</i>	Exocoetidae	✠	<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Parexocoetus brachypterus</i>	Exocoetidae	✓	<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	Lutjanidae	V
<i>Prognichthys sealei</i>	Exocoetidae	✠	<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Prognichthys tringa</i>	Exocoetidae	✠	<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Lutjanidae	V
<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Tomicodon chilensis</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Tomicodon petersii</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	Tripterygiidae	RE	<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis cantherina</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Ekemblemaria sp.</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R	<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	Sparidae	R
<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Cilus gilberti</i>	Sciaenidae	✠
<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	Blenniidae	V	<i>Corvula macrops</i>	Sciaenidae	R
<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	Malakichthyidae	R	<i>Cynoscion phoxocephalus</i>	Sciaenidae	✠
<i>Cookeolus japonicus</i>	Priacanthidae	✓	<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	Sciaenidae	V

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 7)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Pareques perissa</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus compressus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus perrico</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R
<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Diplectrum macropoma</i>	Serranidae	∇	<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Hyporthodus cijfuentesii</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	Ammodytidae	R
<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	Uranoscopidae	V
<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Bellator farrago</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Mycteroperca xenarcha</i>	Serranidae	∇	<i>Peristedion barbiger</i>	Triglidae	∇
<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Paralabrax humeralis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Prionotus miles</i>	Triglidae	RE
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Prionotus stephanophrys</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskerii</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	Anthiidae	V	<i>Pontinus sp. C</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Pontinus strigatus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Pontinus vaughani</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	V	<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Decodon melasma</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	Labridae	V	<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres melanotis</i>	Labridae	V	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	Scorpaenidae	V
<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	Labridae	R			
<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	Labridae	R			

TABLE 9 cont. (p. 8)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	Scorpaenidae	R	<i>Ogocephalus darwini</i>	Ogocephalidae	RE
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Abantennarius coccineus</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	Kuhliidae	R	<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	Antennariidae	V
<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	Oplegnathidae	R	<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Kyphosidae	V	<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	Antennariidae	R
<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	Chaunacidae	R
<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	Melanocetidae	R
<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Kyphosidae	R	<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Girella freminvillii</i>	Girellidae	RE	<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Cirrhichthys oxycephalus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R	<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Cirrhites rivulatus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R	<i>Cryptopsaras coueseii</i>	Ceratiidae	R
<i>Oxyrrhites typus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R	<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	Gigantactinidae	R
<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	Epigonidae	R	<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	Linophrynidae	R
<i>Howella pammelas</i>	Howellidae	R	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	Lobotidae	V	<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	Pomacanthidae	R	<i>Mola mola</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	Pomacanthidae	V	<i>Ranzania laevis</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	Diodontidae	V
<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Diodon eydouxii</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Diodon holacanthus</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	Luvaridae	R	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae	R	<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	Ostraciidae	V
<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	Ostraciidae	R
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	Monacanthidae	V
<i>Prionurus laticlavus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae	R
<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	Lophiidae	R	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	Monacanthidae	V
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	Ogocephalidae	RE	<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	Ogocephalidae	RE	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	Ogocephalidae	R	<i>Melichthys niger</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	Ogocephalidae	R	<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	Ogocephalidae	R	<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	Balistidae	R
			<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	Balistidae	R
			<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	Balistidae	V
			<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	Balistidae	V